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EVALUATION OF WORKING POSTURE: AN ACTION RESEARCH STUDY ON DRIVING POSTURE OF BUS DRIVERS IN SOUTH CEBU

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ABSTRACT

Title : **EVALUATION OF WORKING POSTURE: AN ACTION RESEARCH STUDY ON DRIVING POSTURE OF BUS DRIVERS IN SOUTH CEBU**

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This study investigates the working posture of bus drivers at New Librando Transit Inc. in South Cebu, focusing on ergonomic concerns associated with prolonged seated driving. It examines the anthropometric body dimensions of bus drivers, their driving postures, and the ergonomic fit of the bus cabins and seats. Utilizing the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) method and anthropometry, the study assesses the posture-related risks and ergonomic discrepancies between driver dimensions and seat design. The research includes 20 bus drivers aged 39-59 years old with over five years of experience. Findings reveal significant ergonomic risk in bus drivers' driving posture, suggesting a need for intervention to reduce risks of musculoskeletal disorders, enhance comfort, and promote driver well-being. Specific areas of concern include the driver's wrist angles, sustained arm flexion, and slight forward bending of the neck and trunk. However, anthropometric body measurements did not show significant relationships in dimensions of the bus driver cabins, except abdominal depth-to-steering distance, elbow angle with gear, and buttock knee length, having little effect on posture and comfort. Regardless, recommendations for ergonomic improvements (i.e. regular breaks and stretching exercises) aim to improve occupational health, productivity, and road safety within the local transport sector.

Keywords: *Working posture, Driving Posture, MSD, RULA, anthropometry, bus drivers*

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CHAPTER 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS SCOPE

INTRODUCTION

Rationale of the Study

The transportation industry forms the backbone of modern society, connecting people, businesses, and communities across the globe with unparalleled convenience and efficiency in minimal time. At the heart of this intricate web of mobility, buses dominate public transportation (Badilla et al., 2023). Bus drivers play a pivotal role in navigating a complex network of routes ensuring the seamless flow of passengers and goods. Despite their crucial role, these dedicated professionals frequently endure suboptimal working postures. This can result in discomfort, health problems like work-related musculoskeletal disorders (Das et al., 2022), and reduced job satisfaction. The nature of their profession, often characterized by long hours of continuous seated work and the misfit of the workspace environment, raises significant concerns about their working posture and its impact on their well-being.

Working posture refers to the body's position during work, encompassing both static and dynamic situations (Carini et al., 2017). Posture is crucial for maintaining balance, achieving maximum stability, minimal energy expenditure, and minimal stress on anatomical structures, as described by Pastorelli & Pasquetti (2013). Maintaining correct posture is essential for minimizing strain on the body, ensuring a balanced musculoskeletal state, and protecting supporting structures to prevent damage or progressive deformations in various positions, including standing, lying down, and sitting (Kim et al., 2015). Adopting good working posture is indicative of safe, comfortable, and productive work, while awkward postures increase the risk of musculoskeletal disorders, causing pain or injury in the skeletal muscle system. The

impact of working posture extends to the comfort and productivity of manual labor (Djiono & Noya, 2013).

Professions like driving, requiring prolonged seated postures, pose challenges in maintaining correct posture (Cho et al., 2014). Individuals tend to develop habits like slouching and perpetuating bad posture despite recognizing its incorrectness and desire to maintain correct posture. Habitual adoption of incorrect postures, especially from a young age, can lead to strain on the spine, pelvis, muscles, tendons, joints, bones, and discs, resulting in fatigue and deformation (Carter & Banister, 1994). In the study of Gede et al. (2023); Ghasemi et al. (2018); and Robb and Mansfield (2007) awkward posture, vehicle-road vibrations, lifting, strong movements, and engaging in high-intensity manual work contribute to health risks, namely musculoskeletal disorders. It often affects the muscles, tendons, ligaments, joints, peripheral nerves, and supporting blood vessels on the lower back, spine, shoulders, buttocks, lower legs (Estember & Espinosa, 2020), and neck (Das et al., 2022). The study by Das and colleagues (2022), found that 81% of American drivers had low back torment due to poor posture, followed by 49% of Swedish drivers. Bus drivers, as a professional group, are extensively involved in high-risk operations over prolonged periods (Xi et al., 2023). Kompier & Martino (1995), Magnusson et al. (1996), Tse et al. (2007), Tuchsén and Endahl (1999), and Wang and Lin (2001) indicate that bus drivers experience higher levels of work-related stress compared to individuals in various other occupations.

In addition, developing poor posture causes fatigue, one of the primary factors of accidents in which the drivers feel tired and lose concentration (Beaulieu, 2005). Such task-related factors may contribute to impairing driver alertness and performance, thus compromising the safety of the transport (Das et al., 2022),

impacting passenger safety and overall transportation efficiency as well as decreasing the company's profit (Pastorelli & Pasquetti, 2013). Any impairment in their health conditions can have adverse consequences for drivers, passengers, and operators alike (Chung & Wong, 2011). In the study of Bylund et al., (1997), he revealed that drivers of delivery cars, light cargo vehicles, taxis, buses, and heavy trucks had the highest incidence of injuries per employed individual, accounting for 28% of total permanent impairment cases and 43% of fatalities compared to other occupational groups (Bylund et al., 1997). Given their working conditions and job characteristics, professional bus drivers are particularly susceptible to specific health problems (Chung & Wong, 2011). According to the National Transport Commission of Australia in a study of Powning et al., (2004), professional drivers are classified as safety-critical or high-level safety workers, highlighting the direct relationship between bus drivers and the safety of public transport operations.

Furthermore, the health issues faced by bus drivers are also influenced by the conditions in their workplace. The primary objective of a driver's seat is to facilitate a comfortable and safe driving experience (Smith et al., 2015). However, certain workplace environments lack ergonomic design, leading to discomfort and irritation and increasing the risk of musculoskeletal disorders (Obinna et al., 2021). In this work setting, the furniture used by drivers plays a crucial role in promoting proper postures and, consequently, has implications for productivity. It is crucial for driver's furniture to meet the specific requirements of bus drivers (Savanur et al., 2007).

Both field studies, as well as controlled laboratory experiments, have demonstrated that the work environment significantly impacts individuals in various ways (Appel-Meulenbroek, Clippard, & Pfnür, 2018). Therefore, aligning the workplace with the needs of employees is essential. For instance, the workspace should allow

for the adjustment of postures (Yeats, 1997), leading to improved sitting and task behaviors among bus drivers who use furniture tailored to their body size (Wingrat & Exner, 2005). In this context, it is vital that the workspace, defined as the area where work is performed, is designed to enhance health and well-being without compromising effectiveness (Nicholson, 1991).

In the Philippines, where public transportation plays an integral role in daily life, the comfort and health of bus drivers are intrinsically tied to the efficiency and safety of the transportation system. Professional bus drivers, who have less support from advanced technologies than trained operators and pilots, require more cautious health management (Chung & Wong, 2011). However, limited studies have been done on the evaluation of the driving posture of bus drivers in the Philippines, particularly in South Cebu. Most studies on the evaluation of working posture are conducted in developed or high-income countries and have mostly been carried out abroad. Acknowledging the urgency of addressing these issues as well as the scarcity of studies focused on bus drivers in the Philippines, our research embarks on a comprehensive action research study focused on the working posture of bus drivers of New Librando Transit Inc., a private transportation company in South Cebu, using Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) method, and anthropometric measurement tools. RULA is an ergonomic method designed for the assessment of the upper body's working body (Gede et al., 2023). According to findings from a study by Dempsey et al. (2005), the RULA method stands out as the most commonly employed technique by international ergonomic experts because of its suitability and user-friendly procedure. In Indonesia, the analysis of working posture using the RULA method has been extensively implemented in diverse industrial tasks (Djiono & Noya, 2013). On the contrary, anthropometric measurement tools exhibit a high level of accuracy when assessing

the human body and its various dimensions (Kurniawan et al., 2023). Employing anthropometry is a crucial aspect of tailoring workspace design to suit individual workers (Nicholson, 1991).

This study aims to shed light on the complex relationship between the driving postures, anthropometric measurements of bus drivers, and dimensions of bus driver cabins, employing a comprehensive approach that combines observation, evaluation, analysis, and practical intervention. By investigating the ergonomic challenges faced by New Librando Transit Inc. bus drivers in South Cebu, we aim not only to understand the underlying factors concerning anthropometric measurements, driving posture, and workspace dimensions but also collaboratively develop and propose effective solutions. The goal is clear: to enhance the working conditions of bus drivers, improve their health and well-being, and ultimately contribute to the efficiency and safety of South Cebu's public transportation system. Moreover, the insights gained from this research have the potential to inform policy decisions of the company and the government and may shape future interventions.

Theoretical Background

In the middle of the 20th century, the exploration of occupational health in urban bus drivers began, with Morris and colleagues' work (1953) highlighting the potentially harmful nature of professional bus driving, a concern that persists today. Numerous reviews, such as those by Evans (1994); and Kompier and di Martino (1995), have been conducted in this field. The Journal of Occupational Psychology even dedicated an entire 1998 issue to studies on urban mass-transit operators.

This section introduces the theoretical foundation for the study, focusing on working posture and the implications of workspace environments for bus drivers, setting the stage for our action research study in South Cebu. The fundamental theories guiding this study are James R. Edwards, Robert D. Caplan, and Richard V. Harrison's "Person-Environment Fit Theory: Conceptual Foundations, Empirical Evidence, and Directions for Future Research" (1998), and Max Banfield's "Posture Theory" (2001), which emphasizes the interactions between individuals, their health, work environments, and potential ergonomic interventions.

1. Person-Environment Fit Theory

The Person-Environment Theory, widely embraced in industrial settings and management, centers on the relationship between individuals and their environment, emphasizing the importance of compatibility for well-being and performance (Parsons, 1909; Appel-Meulenbroek & Danivska, 2021).

Person-Environment Fit (P-E Fit) theory does not have a single identifiable author who can be credited as its sole founder, as it has evolved over time with contributions from various scholars. While it lacks a single identifiable founder, Frank Parsons's work, particularly "Choosing a Vocation" (1909), is considered one of the

earliest and most influential. Subsequent developments and refinement by James R. Edwards, Robert D. Caplan, and Richard V. Harrison, as evident in their seminal work "Person-Environment Fit Theory: Conceptual Foundations, Empirical Evidence, and Directions for Future Research" (1998), are frequently referenced in organizational psychology and the study of the work environment.

Person–environment fit refers to a specific person–situation interaction involving the alignment between corresponding person and environment dimensions (Caplan, 1987; French et al., 1974; Ostroff & Schulte, 2007). 'Fit' is assessed through explicit comparisons of person and environment characteristics (Kristof-Brown & Billsberry, 2013). Fit theories emphasize three principles: (1) fit as a more powerful predictor of individual outcomes than its components alone, (2) optimal outcomes when personal and environmental attributes are compatible, and (3) the proposition that discrepancies (misfits) reduce positive outcomes regardless of their direction (Schneider, 2006; Parsons, 1909).

The work environment influences people in various ways, underscoring the importance of aligning the workplace with employee needs (Appel-Meulenbroek, Clippard, & Pfnür, 2018). Post-occupancy evaluations (POEs) and subjective well-being measures are employed to explore how P–E fit theory determines workplace design 'fit' based on individual behavior (Appel-Meulenbroek & Danivska, 2021). POEs, undertaken after a work environment is occupied, assess the functionality of workplace features and their support for effective job completion. Quantitative and qualitative approaches in POEs evaluate the contribution of workplace design to productivity and performance, with over 52 rating tools worldwide for this purpose (Appel-Meulenbroek & Danivska, 2021). Regarded as the principal method for P–E fit

analysis, regression analysis allows an in-depth examination of the interaction between person and environment concepts within a workplace (Edwards et al., 1998).

The importance of PE-fit has been demonstrated across various contexts, though explicit application to the physical work environment remains limited (Hoendervanger et al., 2018). This may stem from the tendency in workplace literature to overlook the work environment as a significant component of the work process (Baldry, 1999).

To better align the physical workplace with the workforce, disciplines from the social sciences and humanities, such as psychology, sociology, and anthropology, offer potential relevance (Appel-Meulenbroek & Danivska, 2021). Anthropometry, the measurement of human dimensions, is crucial for designing workspaces that prioritize comfort, fit, safety, usability, and overall user satisfaction (Hanson et al., 2009). In this context, designing the workspace to promote health and well-being without compromising effectiveness is essential (Nicholson, 1991).

2. The Posture Theory

Banfield's Posture Theory began as a 16-page pamphlet in 1994, evolving into a comprehensive hardback publication by 2000. It consolidates diverse information from various sources, such as research papers in medical journals, natural health magazines, and general and history literature, aiming to cover all aspects of the relationship between posture and health into one unified reference.

The theory stands on the premise of applying proper posture in overall health. The term "posture" is used to describe how someone sits or stands and is generally distinguished between the termed "good posture" and "bad posture". Commonly accepted as an optimal stance, good posture involves effortlessly aligning the head

directly above the spine, maintaining a straight and vertical position with slight natural curves in the lower back and neck—forming a subtle S-shape. This alignment is widely acknowledged for its positive associations with attributes such as a pleasing appearance, overall well-being, strength, and endurance. For thousands of years, Yoga and Buddhism have placed great emphasis on the importance of good posture in achieving a relaxed state of mind. Conversely, "bad posture" is described by the positioning of the head and shoulders forward of the spine, causing an excessive S-shape or a C-shape curvature in the spine. This is often described as a slouched or hunchbacked posture. Bad posture is commonly regarded as poor posture, and poor appearance, and is associated with various health issues, including backaches, poor breathing, exhaustion, and fatigue.

Poor posture is primarily caused by poor nutrition, and infectious illnesses during childhood. The other main factors are the postural forces on the spine and the duration of those forces. Poor posture causes chronic neck, shoulder pain, and back pain, arthritis, and injuries to the spine over time because it forces the head and shoulders to protrude forward from the spine, placing stress and strains on the surrounding muscles and joints. In addition, poor posture places the head and shoulders above the chest and abdomen, putting downward pressure on all those structures (e.g., heart, lungs, stomach, bowels, kidneys, and every ligament and muscle supporting them, and every nerve and tube connecting them) from the weight of the body. For instance, it applies pressure on the chest, resulting in lower left and right-side rib tenderness, soreness, and sporadic pains. It can also put a strain on the muscles on the extreme left and right side of the chest, causing occasional severe and painful muscle cramps in those areas. Furthermore, poor posture can affect the

circulation of blood adversely to cause lethargy, impede blood flow to the brain, and influence such things as the ability to concentrate and tiredness, etc.

2.1. Standing Position

When a person stands upright, their body weight is naturally distributed along the spine, which has evolved to bear the load without difficulty or strain. However, if the person leans forward their center of gravity is thrown forward from the spine, transferring upper body weight to the front chest and abdomen, causing strain on skeletal muscles. Those temporary changes do not affect a person's health, but prolonged stooping can lead to chest and stomach pains and other health problems.

2.2. Sitting Position

When sitting upright the weight of the head and chest is distributed evenly down the bones of the spine, but leaning forward stretches lower spine muscles, potentially causing lower back pain. When the spine is bent forward and the head tilts upward and backward, the additional curvature in the neck exerts abnormal pressure on the discs in the central neck region. This strain affects the muscles, ligaments, and nerves in that area, leading to neck discomfort and potentially contributing to headaches. Furthermore, when the shoulders slouch forward, they extend beyond the chest, causing the combined weight of the head and shoulders to compress the chest cavity, which contains the heart, lungs, and respiratory muscles. The compression of the heart can result in a more noticeable and easily felt heartbeat, increasing susceptibility to palpitations. Simultaneously, pressure on the respiratory muscles may induce cramping and hinder the upward movement of the diaphragm. This impediment makes breathing more energy-intensive, resulting in shallower and less efficient breaths. The pressure on the air in the chest can act like a tourniquet and impede the blood flow

from the feet to the heart, and through the chest to the brain causing difficulty concentrating, or thinking, faintness, and fatigue.

Another significant factor contributing to poor posture is the way a person sits. This is not merely during passive relaxation in a slouched position but particularly when external forces are at play, such as consistently leaning forward at awkward angles while interacting with a desk. In instances where the chair, desk, or computer screen is shaped or positioned in a way that strains different parts of the spine, it compels the spine into unnatural curves. Hence, the seated position is a common source of challenges in maintaining good posture, particularly noticeable during activities like driving or using a computer. When we are engrossed in these tasks, we tend to protrude the head and neck forward. Because the body follows the head, the thoracic and lumbar spine follow suit by rounding forward. This misalignment disrupts the natural balance of the head and upper body over the spinal column, requiring heightened muscular effort and stretching spinal ligaments for support. Over time, this leads to fatigue and eventually results in discomfort and pain in the neck and upper back. Essentially, poor sitting posture can contribute to neck aches, headaches, chest pain, breathing difficulties, and circulatory issues. Nevertheless, these effects don't arise from a single instance of leaning forward but are rather connected to the fact that prolonged poor posture places repetitive strain on the muscles and tissues between the ribs. Over time, this continuous pressure gradually generates tenderness in the region, occasionally leading to sharp, stabbing pains.

2.3. Leaning from the Hips Instead of the Waist

Ultimately, the manner in which an individual consistently leans forward, combined with various contributing factors, impacts the manifestation of symptoms. For instance, when someone with a shallow chest leans forward from the waist, the

spine bends in the middle, causing the breastbone to move backward. This results in a heightened pressure within the chest, increasing the probability of developing more frequent and severe symptoms over time. By contrast, leaning from the hips maintains a straight spine and the breastbone doesn't move, reducing pressure on internal structures.

Regardless, poor posture is unlikely to cause problems such as back pain and chest pain in the first few years of life, but it can have a more serious effect if it gradually changes the shape of the spine and becomes permanent as the person develops into late adulthood, contributing to musculoskeletal disorders. Improper seating posture is potentially unhealthy and considered one of the major contributing factors for several musculoskeletal disorders (MSD) such as pain in the lower back part and shoulder, thighs, ankles, and knees.

Improving posture alleviates pressure on various body parts, reducing the incidence of backaches, chest pains, palpitations, breathlessness, and fatigue, and improving the sense of well-being and physical development. However, it is impossible to straighten adult bones by just sitting up straight. But the problem can be managed by developing a good understanding of anatomy, and by using methods of sitting and standing which restore effortless balance. One of the methods used is the Alexander Technique, which partly involves raising the head so that the spine straightens out, and then finding a position of balance where the head is directly above the spine and feet so that good posture can be maintained by balance, rather than by straining the muscles to stop the body from falling forward or backward. In addition, Yoga and physical exercises are some of the methods used to mitigate work-related problems. On the other hand, based on the Person-environment theory, improper posture can be prevented by addressing factors in the workspace environment and applying

anthropometry, ergonomics, biomechanics, and human factors engineering considerations. The focus needs to be on employees and their needs as they are affected by the work environment and the flow-on effects of employee's well-being on performance and productivity. Efficient and effective workplace design must balance out different personalities and behaviors to ensure maximum creativity and productivity (Baldry, 1999). Workplace design refers to the physical and digital characteristics of the work environment (Appel Meulenbroek & Danivska, 2021). The theory governing this study is presented in Figure 1.

This research adopts a Systems Approach to working posture, acknowledging the complex interplay of physical and anthropometric factors. The theory of Person-Environment Fit offers a systematic framework for understanding how the compatibility between individuals and their workplace environment impacts diverse outcomes, including job satisfaction, performance, and well-being. The Posture Theory provides a structured framework for understanding how working postures affect bus driver comfort and health and highlights the significance of proper working posture for bus drivers. The central hypothesis from these theories posits that enhancing bus drivers' working posture through ergonomic interventions will increase job satisfaction, reduce health issues, and improve road safety.

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework

Review of Related Literature

a. Occupational Safety and Health on Working Posture

The role of working posture in an occupational setting is a crucial element in ensuring the general well-being and efficiency of employees. Among various professions, bus drivers tasked with navigating diverse terrains and traffic conditions constitute a group facing ergonomic challenges. Their occupational demands involve prolonged periods of sitting, frequently in less-than-optimal conditions, potentially affecting both their musculoskeletal health and overall job satisfaction. A program that effectively deals with all aspects of health and safety in the workplace and has a strong focus on the primary prevention of hazards is Occupational Safety and Health (1998). According to the International Labour Organization in the study of Kompier and Martino (1995) "Occupational safety and health is identified as the discipline dealing with the prevention of work-related injuries and diseases as well as the protection and promotion of the health of workers." It pertains to concerns related to health, safety, and welfare issues in the workplace, placing a significant emphasis on the prevention of occupational diseases. One of the recognized contributions of occupational diseases and emerging ergonomics issues is prolonged sedentary behavior (Coenen et al., 2017).

b. Sedentary Behavior

Over the past ten years, there has been a notable surge in the significance of studying sedentary behavior within the scientific community. This is evident from the roughly five-fold increase in the yearly volume of scientific publications addressing sedentary behavior and its associated risk, observed from 2005 to 2014 (Parry & Straker, 2013). Additionally, scientific findings have been extensively disseminated to

the public through mass media, heightening community awareness about the significant health risks associated with sedentary behavior. Accordingly, an ergonomics society has issued a position paper underscoring the hazards associated with sedentary behavior as well as an 'expert consensus' statement providing recommendations regarding sedentary behavior.

According to Tremblay et al. (2017), Sedentary behavior is defined as a specific set of actions carried out while seated or reclined, involving minimal energy expenditure. The amount of sedentary behavior appears to have increased in recent decades in many societies, with an estimated increase of 43% and 47% in overall sedentary behavior since the 1960s in the populations of the USA and UK, respectively (Ng & Popkin, 2012). Occupational sedentary behavior also appears to have increased. In the study of Church et al. (2011), the percentage of American workers engaged in sedentary jobs rose from approximately 15% in 1960 to around 25% by 2010. Recent data from Denmark indicate swift shifts in occupational sitting duration, experiencing a rise of 13 minutes per day from 2007 to 2010. Research employing objective tools like accelerometers has estimated that, within the work period, a cohort of office workers accumulates an average daily sedentary time of 7.3 hours, measured through sitting activities (Parry & Straker, 2013). Moreover, individuals in non-office-based occupations, including bus drivers, can also accumulate substantial periods of sitting during work hours. According to statistics from the United States Bureau of Labor Statistics in the study of Church et al., (2011), bus drivers, on average, spend 82.4% of their workday in a seated position.

c. Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders

Among occupational jobs where employees spend the majority of their day seated include bus drivers, school or special client staff, who, on average, sit for about 82.4% of their workday, as well as accountants (80.7%), and insurance sales agents (80.3%) (Office for National Statistics, 2011). One of the adverse health outcomes of poor working posture is musculoskeletal disorder or MSD (European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, 2024). Musculoskeletal conditions place notable constraints on movement and physical abilities, resulting in early retirement from the workforce, lower levels of well-being, and decreased engagement in societal activities. As per a report, by the National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health of the USA (NIOSH), work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSDs) rank second among diseases associated with employment. According to national statistics from the World Health Organization (2022), around 1.7 billion individuals live with various musculoskeletal conditions globally, encompassing issues like lower back pain, neck ailments, bone fractures, rheumatoid arthritis, etc.

Occupations with the highest rates of Work-related Musculoskeletal Disorders (WRMSDs) are agriculture and forestry, construction, transport, storage (Goggins et al., 2022), and business office administration. Various studies have emerged to assess working posture and its ergonomics risks and rapid exposure in different occupational groups, including taxi drivers, jeepney drivers, tricycle drivers, and bus drivers. For example, the study of Singh et al. (2020), Daneshmandi et al. (2017), Poochada and Chaiklieng (2015), and Amit and Song (2021), assessed the ergonomic risk of sitting posture during work in office workers (Daneshmandi et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2020), and call center employees (Amit & Song, 2021; Poochada & Chaiklieng, 2015), respectively. The findings revealed a high risk of developing musculoskeletal disorders

among employees, particularly in the lower back (85%), neck (80%), shoulders (55%), upper back (80%), thighs (40%), and knees (90%), primarily due to factors such as prolonged sitting, extensive computer usage, and frequent calls with customers (Poochada & Chaiklieng, 2015). They concluded that musculoskeletal disorders are associated with posture in an office setting. Daneshmandi et al.(2017) concluded that factors like sex, age, BMI, job tenure, marital status, educational level, and workstation comfort were associated with sitting time during work. In addition, factors like exhaustion, job dissatisfaction, hypertension, and musculoskeletal symptoms are said to be associated with prolonged sitting.

In a transportation setting, researchers Majid et al. (2018) and Seva et al. (2011), found that there is a significant relationship between discomfort experienced by elderly drivers (Majid et al., 2018) and jeepney drivers (Seva et al., 2011) due to seat design, and various factors such as BMI, smoking status, driving until midnight, and back pain. The design of the car seat caused discomfort in most respondents' body parts (92.5%). The lower back (3.3%), right buttock (62.5%), and left buttock (61.7%) were the most frequently impacted body parts. Research has indicated that compared to other professions, taxi drivers have a higher chance of getting MSDs (Bulduk et al., 2014; Majid et al., 2018). According to Bulduk et al. (2014), taxi drivers are highly exposed to risk factors due to restricted postures, repetitive movements, vibration, continuous attention to the road, and work-related stress. High exposure was also linked to increased age and years of service.

Conversely, Hasan et al. (2023) found that occupational truck drivers who operate whole-body vehicles experienced the highest incidence of musculoskeletal disorders. This is attributed to drivers being susceptible to various occupational injuries due to demanding physical work conditions, including prolonged periods of sitting,

exposure to noise, fluctuations in temperature, awkward sitting positions, and whole-body vibrations.

On another subject, among the tricycle drivers in the Kano metropolis, Nigeria studied by Abba et al. (2016), there was a significant relationship between the drivers' experienced pain in various body parts such as hips, thighs, or buttocks, with ankle pain being the most common and the duration of work. The study by Arminas (2019) also discusses the ergonomic risks faced by public transportation drivers in Makassar City. The findings indicated that drivers suffered from pain in different body parts such as the back, waist, hips, buttocks, and legs, attributed to their sitting position and the condition of the car seat. Furthermore, the research highlighted that public transport drivers endure discomfort in various body areas due to prolonged driving hours without breaks, outdated car facilities, and non-ergonomic modifications.

Other research on bus drivers indicates that there is a high prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders particularly in the lower back, neck, upper arms, lower legs, and wrists on the working posture of bus drivers from semi-urban areas in India (Das et al., 2022). Das et al.(2022) also found that there was a relationship between musculoskeletal disorders and years of driving. A study by Saftarina, Mayasari, & Octaviani (2017) also investigated the work posture of inter-provincial bus drivers and its association with musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) in Bandar Lampung City. It was found that 73.3% of people had MSDs, the majority of which were found in the lumbar back (36.48%), calves (31.08%), and shoulders (28.38%). Studies show that physical workload, pain-related fear, employment duration, body posture, smoking habits, job experience, body mass index (BMI), and age can influence the development of MSDs. They also indicate that static and unergonomic postures, along with long-lasting vibrations, are risk factors for MSD, which can lead to road accidents.

In similar studies in the same country, Yasobant, Chandran & Reddy (2015) examined the risk of work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) among bus drivers in Chennai, India. The findings revealed that bus drivers are at a high risk of developing WMSDs, particularly in the back (24%), neck (26%), shoulders (20%), and wrists (20%) regions. The regions of lowest complaints were knees and ankles. Risk scores indicated many drivers were at high risk of WMSDs, with poor ergonomics and lack of physical activity as contributing factors. Filho et al. (2015) also conducted a research study that discussed the working conditions of bus drivers in Salvador, Brazil. It was revealed that 84% of bus drivers (299 of the total 357 respondents) felt pain in the back, neck, or arms during or after work, significantly impacting their well-being and performance.

d. Driving Posture and Associated Risks

Recent studies emphasize the importance of ergonomic factors in driving posture due to their link with musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) and potential accident risk. For example, Atallah et al. (2022), Pickard et al. (2022), and Tinitali et al. (2019) explored how prolonged driving and poor posture increase lumbar and cervical spine stress, contributing to MSDs in commercial drivers. This research highlighted that postures involving forward head tilt, rounded shoulders, and prolonged sitting directly impact the spine and are highly associated with chronic back and neck pain (Atallah et al., 2022; Pickard et al., 2022; & Tinitali et al., 2019).

Further, a study by Smith et al. (2015) examined the impact of posture on driver safety, revealing that improper seating positions decrease reaction times and impede control over the vehicle. The researchers noted that an ergonomic driving setup significantly reduces driver fatigue and enhances reaction speeds, which is crucial for

high-risk professions like bus and truck driving (Smith et al., 2015). Similarly, Nazerian et al. (2018), and Okunribido et al. (2008) identified that body vibrations experienced during long drives further exacerbate ergonomic risks, especially when paired with awkward or constrained postures, which could compromise safety and lead to MSDs.

These findings underscore the urgent requirement for interventions aimed at optimizing driver posture through seat design, work breaks, and ergonomic training, aiming to reduce the risk of posture-related health issues among drivers.

e. Ergonomic Assessment Methods for Evaluating Postures and Musculoskeletal Disorders

For the evaluation of different working postures, various methods have been presented. Most of the studies have used the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) approach for ergonomic analysis (Amit & Song, 2021; Arminas, 2019; Das et al., 2022; Yasobant et al., 2015; Seva et al., 2011). The RULA approach calculates the musculoskeletal loading of upper extremities such as the upper arms, forearms, wrists, wrist twists, neck, trunk, and legs. Several studies have also used the Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) approach (Saftarina et al., 2017; Amit & Song, 2021; Yasobant et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2020). The Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) method evaluates and gauges the postural risks associated with work across the entire body. A few studies, such as Amit and Song (2021) and Yasobant et al. (2015), used both RULA and REBA to measure work posture to estimate the degree of MSD risk. These approaches exhibit a strong correlation in pinpointing crucial work sites and identifying critical limbs. Accordingly, it is recommended to employ both methods for assessing risk factors related to work-related musculoskeletal disorders in various industries.

In identifying factors associated with discomfort in computer-related tasks, certain studies utilized the Rapid Office Strain Assessment (ROSA) (Poochada & Chaiklieng, 2015). This tool evaluates sitting posture, workstation elements (such as chair height, pan depth, armrest, and back support), computer peripherals (including monitor, mouse, and keyboard), telephone usage, and the duration of time spent on each posture or activity.

In collecting personal data and musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs), studies have utilized a self-administered questionnaire using Nordic Musculoskeletal Questionnaires (NMQ) (Daneshmandi et al., 2017; Yasobant et al., 2015) to assess symptoms and examine reported cases of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) in different body regions among the study population. Some studies used the Cornell Musculoskeletal Disorder Questionnaire (CMDQ)(Das et al., 2022) to determine the discomfort location and common types of MSDs among bus drivers and assess the frequency and extent of pain felt in each body segment during their work period.

Conversely, few studies utilized the Nordic Body Map (NBM) (Arminas, 2019) to assess ergonomic risk levels associated with drivers' positions and assess musculoskeletal problems to determine the distribution of MSDs on the body.

f. Ergonomic Interventions to Mitigate Work-Related Musculoskeletal Disorders

In assessing the working posture and determining its adverse effects, the existing literature emphasized the importance of implementing ergonomic interventions in workstations (such as redesigning chairs and tables (Poochada & Chaiklieng, 2015; Singh et al., 2020), and sit-stand (Daneshmandi et al., 2017)), adjusting sitting postures, incorporating breaks for continuous work (Poochada &

Chaiklieng, 2015; Singh et al., 2020), and administering workplace health promotion activities to alleviate the risk of WMSDs and improve the comfort and efficiency of employees.

g. Identified Literature Gaps and the Need for Comprehensive Ergonomic Studies

However, the study identified several gaps in the existing literature, which includes a comprehensive analysis of the specific ergonomic factors contributing to the high risk of musculoskeletal disorders among employees and a detailed analysis of the specific physical discomfort experienced by bus drivers, such as the types of pain and their frequency. The study does not delve enough into specific design flaws of equipment that contribute to poor sitting posture and musculoskeletal disorders. Furthermore, the study did not explore the potential economic or organizational barriers to enforcing a new design workstation in the workplace, such as cost or space limitations. They also did not measure the effectiveness, cost-effectiveness, and feasibility of a new design workstation or ergonomic interventions in reducing prolonged sitting among workers. Gaps also include limited demographics or insufficient sample size to represent the entire population potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings and may not be generalizable to other regions or countries. Moreover, other studies relied on self-reported data which may introduce bias and may affect the accuracy of the findings.

To conclude, numerous studies from foreign countries have been conducted to examine the relationships between working posture and the onset of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). It was stated that MSD impacts the joints, muscles, tendons, ligaments, nerves, etc. (Majid et al., 2018), and high-risk work posture is a significant

factor for MSD in bus drivers from foreign countries. Most studies used Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) as a research measurement tool, and Nordic Musculoskeletal Disorders (NMQ) as a data collection method. The study determined that ergonomic risks arise from static postures, repetitive movements, awkward positions, and vibrations. The driving position poses a significant ergonomic risk, and the study suggests implementing changes to prevent further injuries. Emphasis is placed on the importance of addressing work posture to decrease the occurrence of Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) and enhance the well-being of bus drivers. However, the study identified several gaps in the existing literature such as the effectiveness, cost-effectiveness, and feasibility of a proposed ergonomic intervention in reducing prolonged sitting among workers. Gaps also include limited demographics to represent the entire population potentially limiting the generalizability of the findings, and insufficient studies in the Philippines. These highlight the need for further research to address these limitations and explore additional factors to develop a more comprehensive understanding of work posture among bus drivers and develop more comprehensive strategies for preventing musculoskeletal disorders and improving ergonomic conditions for bus drivers ensuring the practicality and sustainability of the proposed intervention.

Literature Map

Presented with xmind

Figure 2. Literature Map

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

This study has focused on evaluating the working posture of bus drivers, measuring their body anthropometric dimensions, and conducting an ergonomic evaluation of the bus driver cabins and bus driver seat during the Academic Year 2023-2024 as the basis for an action plan ensuring that the workplace is designed and maintained in such a way that it will continue to provide physical, functional, and psychological comfort for users.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the bus drivers as to:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Years of employment;
 - 1.3. Medical history; and
 - 1.4. Body Mass Index (BMI)?
2. What are the anthropometric measurements of bus drivers, the driving posture with the RULA worksheet, and the dimensions of the bus driver cabins and bus driver seat of the New Librando Transit Inc. bus?
3. What is the distribution of RULA worksheet scores among New Librando Transit Inc. bus drivers, reflecting their working postures during daily operations, ranging from the highest immediate risk of injury to the lowest risk?
4. Is there a significant relationship between anthropometric measurements of bus drivers, and the dimensions of bus driver cabins and bus driver seat of the New Librando Transit Inc. bus?
5. What potential ergonomic interventions and strategies can be employed to enhance the working postures and support the well-being of bus drivers?

Statement of Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant relationship between anthropometric measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of bus driver cabin and seat.

H_a: There is a significant relationship between anthropometric measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of bus driver cabin and seat.

H₀: There is no significant difference between anthropometric measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of bus driver cabin and seat.

H_a: There is a significant difference between anthropometric measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of bus driver cabin and seat.

Scope and Delimitation

This study focuses on evaluating the working posture of bus drivers employed by New Librando Transit Inc., located in South Cebu, Philippines, specifically addressing their driving postures, anthropometric body measurements, and the ergonomic assessment of the bus driver cabins and seats. The research encompasses 20 bus drivers aged between 39-59 years, who have at least five years of employment within the company. The study's primary objective was to assess the correlation between driver body dimensions and cabin or seat dimensions, employing the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) tool for posture evaluation.

This study did not extend to bus drivers from other companies, limiting its generalizability to New Librando Transit Inc. alone. Furthermore, it excludes drivers with prior medical conditions or injuries unrelated to their work, as well as those with severe physical disabilities. The investigation was time-bound to

the Academic Year 2023-2024 and was constrained to the ergonomic conditions currently present in the buses operated by New Librando Transit Inc.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant in addressing the critical issues associated with working posture among bus drivers. The result of this study would be a significant contribution to promoting occupational safety and health and employing ergonomic interventions in different workplaces/workstations and be beneficial to the following entities:

BUS DRIVERS. The result of this study aims to improve working posture which could enhance the comfort and health of bus drivers, reducing the risk of musculoskeletal disorders and fatigue associated with prolonged periods of driving. This could also enhance their productivity and efficiency in the workplace.

TRANSPORTATION COMPANIES/AGENCIES. The result of this study can benefit transportation companies or agencies in implementing changes that improve the working conditions for bus drivers. This could lead to increased job satisfaction, job performance, reduced absenteeism, and potentially lower turnover rates and healthcare costs associated with driver health issues.

OCCUPATIONAL HEALTH AND SAFETY PROFESSIONALS. This will make it easier for occupational health and safety professionals to develop guidelines and recommendations for improving working conditions for bus drivers. This could contribute to broader efforts to enhance workplace safety in the transportation industry.

REGULATORY BODIES. This study's result will help create an action plan to reduce the number of cases of musculoskeletal disorders recorded in the region. Department of Transportation, Department of Labor and Employment, and other government

agencies may find the study useful for updating or implementing regulations related to the working conditions of bus drivers.

EDUCATION. The result of this study may contribute to the existing body of knowledge on ergonomics, occupational health, and transportation safety.

COMMUNITY. A healthier and more comfortable working environment for bus drivers can have positive ripple effects on society by contributing to road safety and the overall well-being of individuals in the workforce. This could also potentially influence other work industries in employing occupational safety and health.

FUTURE RESEARCHERS. The result of this study can serve as a reference for future research in related areas.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method

This research will employ a quantitative methodology to gather numerical data for evaluating the driving posture, and anthropometric body dimensions of bus drivers, and dimensions of bus driver cabins. The researchers will use anthropometric measurement tools to evaluate body dimensions of bus drivers and assess dimensions of bus driver cabins. Following that, a descriptive approach will be utilized to assess whether the driving posture of bus drivers performs an optimal posture or improper posture during the 3-hour trip within South Cebu. Based on the analysis, the researchers will assess significant relationships and significant differences between the working posture, anthropometric body dimensions of bus drivers, and dimensions of bus driver cabins and subsequently propose an ergonomic intervention to address the significant issue of working posture. Ultimately, this initiative seeks to improve the working conditions and well-being of bus drivers, contributing to the efficiency and safety of South Cebu's public transportation system.

Flow of the Study

The whole study was shown in Figure 3 for the research flow of the study, with the use of the process flowchart wherein the following symbols and their usage are described below (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Research flow of the Study

An oval indicates beginning or end of a process.

A parallelogram is a point where there is input or output from the process.

A rectangle act as basic commands and is represented by an action.

A diamond indicates a point where a decision is made.

Arrows indicates the direction and order of process execution.

Figure 4. Process flowchart symbols and usage

Research Environment

The study will be conducted in New Librando Transit Incorporated, a private bus transportation company in South Cebu, at Purok 5 Sineguelas, Barangay Taytay, Badian, Cebu, Philippines. Currently, the number of bus drivers employed in New Librando Transit Inc. is approximately 60 drivers, aged between 35-59 years. The number of buses traveling in a day is within 26-30 bus units with 20-30 minutes intervals. Due to convenience and a great target demographic that may readily assist this study, the researchers chose this place and company as their target research environment.

Figure 5. Location Map of New Librando Transit Inc.

Research Respondents

The study included a stratified sample of 20 respondents, all workers aged 39-59 years, employed at New Librando Transit Inc. stationed at Purok 5 Sineguelas, Barangay Taytay, Badian, Cebu, Philippines. Demographic profiles such as age, years of employment, medical history, height, and weight will be collected. These data will be used to sort out subjects based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria set by the researchers. Included were workers aged 39-59 years, who had been full-time employees at New Librando Transit Inc. for equal and more than 5 years. Exclusion criteria involve subjects with a previous trauma or injury, a history of surgery, severe physical disability causing pain, or any medical condition causing pain, before and after they applied to the company. The study will be conducted during the Academic Year 2023-2024.

Research Instruments

This study will use a structured interview, anthropometric measurement tools, and Rapid Upper Limb Assessment tool. Structured interviews will be used in collecting demographic profiles of bus drivers such as age, years of employment, medical history, height, and weight. Anthropometric measurement tool will be used in measuring body dimensions of bus drivers, and the dimensions of bus driver cabins. The anthropometric characteristics of the bus drivers were measured using a measuring tape, anthropometer, and bevel protractor. Bus driver cabins parameter variables were also measured using a measuring tape, steel tape, and bevel protractors. According to Kurniawan and colleagues (2023), anthropometric measurement tools exhibit a high level of accuracy when assessing the human body and its various dimensions. Employing anthropometry is a crucial aspect of tailoring

workspace design to suit individual workers (Nicholson, 1991). Conversely, the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) tool is a systematic process used to evaluate the driving postures of bus drivers in doing work tasks involving upper limb activities. The assessment tool utilized in this study was developed after reviewing existing methodologies for evaluating working posture (Bowden, 2018; Diego-Mas, 2023; Dempsey et al., 2005; Gede et al., 2023; Djiono & Noya, 2013; Wibowo & Mawadati, 2021) and consulting data from the Handbook of Human Factors and Ergonomics Methods (Bowden, 2018). The Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) tool, created in 1993 by Dr. Lynn McAtamney and Professor E. Nigel Corlett from the University of Nottingham's Institute for Occupational Ergonomics in England (Bowden, 2018; Diego-Mas, 2023), serves as the foundation for this ergonomic assessment. The tool takes into account the biomechanical and postural load requirements associated with job tasks, focusing on the neck, trunk, and upper extremities. A concise, single-page worksheet is employed to assess the required body posture, force exertion, and repetition (Bowden, 2018). Figure 6 shows a sample of the RULA Assessment worksheet (McAtamney & Corlett, 1993).

Scores are recorded for each body region in section A (upper arm, forearm/lower arm, wrist, and wrist twist) and section B (neck, trunk, and legs) based on the evaluations. Subsequently, overall scores for section A and section B are adjusted, considering the type of muscular activity and force applied during the task (Bowden, 2018; Diego-Mas, 2023; Cornell University Ergonomics Web, 1685). As shown in Table 1, risk factor variables are compiled, yielding a single score that reflects the level of musculoskeletal disorder (MSD) risk (Bowden, 2018). The resulting value from the RULA method is proportional to the risk associated with task performance, with higher values indicating an elevated risk of developing musculoskeletal injuries

(Bowden, 2018; Diego-Mas, 2023; Cornell University Ergonomics Web, 1685). The method categorizes these final scores into action levels, aiding the evaluator in decision-making based on the analysis. These levels also determine whether the bus drivers' posture during a 3-hour trip in South Cebu is optimal or improper. The published tool has demonstrated satisfactory validity and reliability, having been tested by McAtamney, Corlett, and other ergonomic experts. It is designed to be a component of a comprehensive ergonomics survey (Bowden, 2018; Diego-Mas, 2023; Cornell University Ergonomics Web, 1685). Figure 7 summarizes the process of obtaining the Action Level in the RULA method (Diego-Mas, 2023).

Table 1. Level of Risk

Action level	RULA Score	Interpretation
1	1-2	The person is working in the best posture with no risk of injury from their work posture.
2	3-4	The person is working in a posture that could present some risk of injury from their work posture, and this score most likely is the result of one part of the body being in a deviated and awkward position, so this should be investigated and corrected.
3	5-6	The person is working in a poor posture with a risk of injury from their work posture, and the reasons for this need to be investigated and changed in the near future to prevent an injury.
4	7+	The person is working in the worst posture with an immediate risk of injury from their work posture, and the reasons for this need to be investigated and changed immediately to prevent an injury.

RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Complete this worksheet following the step-by-step procedure below. Keep a copy in the employee's personnel folder for future reference.

A. Arm & Wrist Analysis

Step 1: Locate Upper Arm Position

Step 1a: Adjust...
 If shoulder is raised: +1;
 If upper arm is abducted: +1;
 If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1

Step 2: Locate Lower Arm Position

Step 2a: Adjust...
 If arm is working across midline of the body: +1;
 If arm out to side of body: +1

Step 3: Locate Wrist Position

Step 3a: Adjust...
 If wrist is bent from the midline: +1

Step 4: Wrist Twist
 If wrist is twisted mainly in mid-range = 1;
 If twist at or near end of twisting range = 2

Step 5: Look-up Posture Score in Table A
 Use values from steps 1,2,3 & 4 to locate Posture Score in table A

Step 6: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static (i.e. held for longer than 1 minute) or;
 If action repeatedly occurs 4 times per minute or more: +1

Step 7: Add Force/load Score
 If load less than 2 kg (intermittent): +0;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (intermittent): +1;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (static or repeated): +2;
 If more than 10 kg load or repeated or shocks: +3

Step 8: Find Row in Table C
 The completed score from the Arm/Wrist analysis is used to find the row on Table C

SCORES

Table A

Upper Arm	Lower Arm	Wrist						
		1	2	3	4			
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3
1	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3
1	3	2	3	3	3	3	4	4
2	1	3	3	3	3	4	4	4
2	2	3	3	3	3	4	4	4
2	3	3	4	4	4	4	5	5
3	1	3	3	4	4	4	5	5
3	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	5
3	3	3	4	4	4	4	5	5
4	1	4	4	4	4	5	5	5
4	2	4	4	4	4	5	5	5
4	3	4	4	4	4	5	5	5
5	1	5	5	5	5	6	6	6
5	2	5	5	5	5	6	6	6
5	3	5	5	5	5	6	6	6
6	1	7	7	7	7	8	8	8
6	2	7	7	7	7	8	8	8
6	3	7	7	7	7	8	8	8

Table B

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Neck	1	2	1	2	1	2
1	1	3	2	3	3	4
2	2	3	2	3	4	5
3	3	3	3	4	4	5
4	4	4	4	4	5	6
5	5	5	5	5	6	7
6	6	6	6	6	7	8

Table C

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5
2	2	2	3	4	4	5	5
3	3	3	3	4	4	5	6
4	3	3	3	4	5	5	6
5	4	4	4	5	6	7	7
6	4	4	4	5	6	7	7
7	5	5	5	6	7	7	7
8	5	5	5	6	7	7	7

B. Neck, Trunk & Leg Analysis

Step 9: Locate Neck Position

Step 9a: Adjust...
 If neck is twisted: +1; If neck is side-bending: +1

Step 10: Locate Trunk Position

Step 10a: Adjust...
 If trunk is twisted: +1; If trunk is side-bending: +1

Step 11: Legs
 If legs & feet supported and balanced: +1;
 If not: +2

Step 12: Look-up Posture Score in Table B
 Use values from steps 9,10 & 11 to locate Posture Score in Table B

Step 13: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static or;
 If action 4/minute or more: +1

Step 14: Add Force/load Score
 If load less than 2 kg (intermittent): +0;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (intermittent): +1;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (static or repeated): +2;
 If more than 10 kg load or repeated or shocks: +3

Step 15: Find Column in Table C
 The completed score from the Neck/Trunk & Leg analysis is used to find the column on Chart C

Final Score =

Subject: _____ Date: / / _____

Company: _____ Department: _____ Scorer: _____

FINAL SCORE: 1 or 2 = Acceptable; 3 or 4 investigate further; 5 or 6 investigate further and change soon; 7 investigate and change immediately

Source: McAtamney, L. & Corlett, E.N. (1993) RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders. Applied Ergonomics, 24(2) 91-99.
 © Professor Alan Hedge, Cornell University. Feb. 2001

Figure 6. Sample of RULA Worksheet (McAtamney & Corlett, 1993)

Figure 7. RULA Process

Data Gathering Procedure

The information will be gathered via interviews with the New Librando Transit Inc. manager stationed in Badian, Cebu, evaluation, and observations from 20 respondents, and assessment on the bus driver cabin of New Librando Transit Inc. bus. The interviews will be conducted in their respective office at Purok 5 Sineguelas, Barangay Taytay, Badian, Cebu, Philippines. The manager and supervisor will be asked for the demographic profile of the bus drivers. Second, evaluation and observations, will be performed on the front seat, beside the driver's seat of the bus, to measure the body dimensions of bus drivers and evaluate their driving posture. Lastly, assessment on the bus driver cabins will be conducted in their bus garage. The objectives of the study will be explained to the manager, supervisor, and respondents.

Statistical Treatment

Percentage

The respondents were converted into percentages by dividing the total frequency represented by each demographic profile by the total number of respondents, and the quotient was multiplied by 100. This formula was used in other tabulated data.

The formula for Percentage:

$$\% = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

$\%$ = *percentage*

f = *frequency of representation of each demographic profile*

N = *the total number of respondents*

Grand Mean

It measures the mean of different sub-means. The average sub mean of four RULA Scores (1-2, 3-4, 5-6, & 7+) and Action levels (1, 2, 3, & 4) in the RULA interpretation table is the grand mean.

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 17.0)

Data collected from anthropometric body dimensions of bus drivers and dimensions of bus driver cabin were processed in Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet 2010 version and imported into SPSS 17.0 for further analysis. Descriptive statistics which included mean, standard deviation, range, and percentiles (5th, 50th and 95th percentiles) were calculated.

Standard Deviation

Standard deviation is a statistic that measures the dispersion of a dataset relative to its mean and is calculated as the square root of the variance. The formula for a standard deviation can be expressed as:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (X - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}}$$

Where;

X = the value in the data distribution

\bar{x} = the sample mean

n = total number of observations

Range

Range is a statistical measurement of dispersion, or how much a given data set is stretched out from smallest to largest. The formula for a range can be expressed as:

$$\text{Range}(X) = \text{Max} - \text{Min}$$

Where;

Maximum/Max = the largest observed value of a variable

Minimum/Min = smallest observed value of a variable

Percentiles

A percentile is a comparison score between a particular score and the scores from the same set. The formula for a percentile can be expressed as:

$$P = \left(\frac{n}{N}\right) \times 100$$

Where;

n = ordinal rank of the given value or value below the number

N = number of values in the data set

P = percentile

Simple Linear Regression

Simple linear regression examine the relationship between one dependent variable and one independent variables. It allows for the consideration of the effects of one predictor on the dependent variable. The equation for a simple linear regression model with p independent variables can be expressed as:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x + \epsilon$$

Where;

Y = is the dependent variable

x = is the independent variable

β_0 = is the constant or intercept

ϵ = is the error term representing random variability and measurement error

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

A t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means is used to determine whether the means of two related groups are statistically different from each other. The equation for a t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means can be expressed as:

$$t = \frac{\sum d}{\sqrt{\frac{n(\sum d^2) - (\sum d)^2}{n - 1}}}$$

Where;

d = difference per paired value

n = number of samples

Definition of Terms

Biomechanical load – refers to the forces, stresses, and strains applied to the human body's tissues, such as muscles, bones, tendons, and joints, during various activities or movements.

Descriptive approach – involves systematically observing, documenting, and presenting facts and characteristics of a phenomenon without manipulating variables.

Driving posture adopted – refers to the specific body position and alignment that a person assumes while operating a vehicle.

Exclusion criteria – are specific characteristics, conditions, or factors that disqualify individuals or elements from participating in a research study, clinical trial, or other investigations.

Improper posture – refers to the alignment of the body's segments that deviates from a balanced and biomechanically efficient position. It involves positions and movements that may strain muscles, ligaments, and joints, potentially leading to discomfort, pain, and musculoskeletal issues over time.

Inclusion criteria – are specific characteristics or criteria that individuals or elements must possess in order to be eligible for participation in a research study, clinical trial, or other investigation.

Optimal posture – refers to the most balanced and biomechanically efficient alignment of the body's various segments, include the head, neck, spine, and limbs, during various activities such as sitting, standing, or moving.

Postural load – refers to the mechanical stresses and strains placed on the musculoskeletal system as a result of maintaining a particular body posture, often for an extended period.

Process flowchart – is a visual representation or diagram that illustrates the sequence of steps and activities involved in a process.

Quantitative methodology – refers to a research approach or set of research methods that primarily relies on the collection and analysis of numerical data to understand, describe, or explain phenomena.

Stratified sample – is a probability sampling method in research where the population is divided into distinct subgroups or strata based on certain characteristics that are relevant to the research question.

Structured interview – is a research method in which a predetermined set of standardized questions is used to gather information from participants.

CHAPTER 2

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data. This chapter is structured into six sections. The first section focuses on profiling the respondents based on socio-demographic variables such as age, years of employment, medical history, and BMI. Following this, the second section presents the anthropometric body measurements of the respondents. The third section evaluates the posture of each respondent using the RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet, specifically assessing whether they exhibit optimal or improper posture during a 3-hour trip within South Cebu. In the fourth section, the dimensions of the bus driver cabin and bus driver seat used by the respondents are detailed. In the fifth section, presents a table that examines significant relationships between the respondent's anthropometry score, and the dimensions of the bus driver cabin and seat utilized. Finally, the last section presents a table that examines significant difference between the respondents' anthropometry score, and the dimensions of the bus driver cabin and seat utilized.

PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

This section shows the profile of the respondents based on their age, years of employment, medical history, and Body Mass Index (BMI).

2.1. Age

Figure 8. Age

Figure 8 illustrates the composition of our respondent pool, accounting for a total of 100 percent of participants. These respondents are categorized into five distinct age ranges, each representing a proportionate share of the overall sample. The results show that the age distribution of the respondents is varied, with a majority falling within the range of 39 to 43 years old, comprising the largest proportion at 35 percent of the total respondents, followed by the group aged 49 to 53 years old at 30 percent. This suggests that the research sample is predominantly composed of middle-aged individuals. Interestingly, there is a smaller but notable presence of respondents aged 59 to 60 years old, constituting 5 percent of the sample. These results showed that middle-aged bus drivers dominated the job in the New Librando Transit Inc. bus company. This is due likely by a combination of factors including job stability, driving experience, financial incentives, work schedule flexibility, job

availability, and personal circumstances of bus drivers. However, this age group is most likely to start to face challenges related to physical health, fatigue, and stress, and should consider ergonomic preventive measures and health initiatives (Holmstrom & Engholm, 2003; Collins & O'Sullivan, 2011).

2.2. Years of Employment

Figure 9. *Years of Employment*

Figure 9 displays the distribution of years of employment among our respondents, totaling 100 percent. The data reveals that a significant portion of bus drivers (30 percent) have worked in their roles for 15-19 years, indicating considerable experience in the profession. Additionally, a small percentage (5 percent) of drivers have been employed for 25 years or more, demonstrating long-term dedication to their roles. However, these experienced drivers may encounter challenges related to posture, such as reduced flexibility and joint stiffness (Oha et al., 2014; Bulduk, 2014). Conversely, drivers with shorter tenure, like those with 5-9 years of employment, may

still be learning about proper working posture and may face a higher risk of postural issues due to prolonged sitting and repetitive movements (Yu, 2009).

2.3. Medical History

Figure 10. Medical History

Figure 10 illustrates the medical conditions reported by our respondents, with a total of 100 percent. The data shows that all bus drivers (100 percent) surveyed indicated no documented medical issues, reflecting a generally healthy population within the sample. This includes the absence of prior hospitalizations, injuries, surgeries, severe disabilities, or chronic health conditions like arthritis, high blood pressure, or diabetes. This indicates that the researcher's inclusion and exclusion criteria were met. With a healthy population, the focus of the RULA assessment can be directed toward ergonomic factors specific to driving posture, seating ergonomics, and workspace setup (Moom et al., 2015; Pochada & Chaiklieng, 2015).

2.4. Body Mass Index (BMI)

Figure 11. *Body Mass Index (BMI)*

Figure 11 presents the distribution of Body Mass Index (BMI) categories among our respondents, with 100 percent total. The data reveals that 50 percent of bus drivers fall into the overweight category, while a smaller percentage (5 percent) are classified as obese based on BMI criteria. These findings indicate potential challenges for drivers in maintaining a balanced and aligned posture, leading to discomfort, fatigue, and an increased risk of musculoskeletal injuries over time (Syah et al., 2022).

RESPONDENT'S ANTHROPOMETRIC BODY MEASUREMENTS

This section focuses on the anthropometric characteristics of bus drivers and presents the statistical analysis outcomes derived from the primary data.

Table 2. Summary of the anthropometric body dimensions of 20 New Librando Transit Inc. bus drivers

P.No.	Anthropometric Body Dimensions	Mean (cm)	Standard Deviation (cm)	5 th Percentile (cm)	50 th Percentile (cm)	95 th Percentile (cm)	Min (cm)	Max (cm)	Range (cm)
P1	Weight	68.850	9.235	54.750	68.500	82.200	50.000	86.000	36.000
P2	Sitting Height	82.555	3.381	77.140	83.000	86.910	76.000	89.000	13.000
P3	Sitting Eye Height	70.055	3.708	62.970	69.800	75.675	62.400	79.000	16.600
P4	Shoulder Width	43.510	3.559	39.285	43.400	48.425	39.000	50.800	11.800
P5	Shoulder Height	53.100	2.391	49.735	53.000	56.000	48.500	56.000	7.500
P6	Head Length	18.115	0.865	17.175	18.000	19.340	16.700	20.100	3.400
P7	Head Breadth	16.125	1.060	14.495	16.000	18.000	14.400	18.000	3.600
P8	Shoulder-Elbow Length	34.675	3.092	30.045	34.600	40.010	29.000	40.200	11.200
P9	Elbow-Wrist Length	27.355	2.924	23.990	26.950	33.000	23.800	33.000	9.200
P10	Hand Length	18.425	0.898	17.180	18.550	19.715	16.800	20.000	3.200
P11	Hand Breadth	10.225	1.085	8.910	10.200	11.605	7.200	11.700	4.500
P12	Elbow rest height	25.940	5.025	19.330	25.050	33.725	18.000	38.000	20.000
P13	Knee Height	53.860	2.938	50.375	53.450	58.050	49.900	59.000	9.100
P14	Buttock-Knee Length	51.855	4.186	46.190	51.200	58.065	46.000	59.300	13.300
P15	Buttock-Popliteal Length	44.325	3.930	38.970	43.950	50.080	38.400	51.600	13.200
P16	Popliteal-Height	46.365	7.730	32.825	46.750	53.440	29.500	67.500	38.000
P17	Hip Breadth	31.640	2.260	28.995	31.250	35.030	27.000	35.600	8.600
P18	Thigh- Clearance Height	12.840	1.951	10.090	12.650	16.400	9.900	16.400	6.500
P19	Abdominal Depth	23.935	4.154	18.440	24.600	31.245	17.300	32.100	14.800
P20	Abdominal-Steering	9.985	3.553	4.950	9.000	15.860	4.000	17.000	13.000
P21	Chest-Steering	41.425	8.749	34.365	42.150	50.035	9.000	50.700	41.700
P22	Foot Length	27.565	2.230	23.975	27.650	31.050	23.500	32.000	8.500
P23	Foot Breadth	8.640	1.949	5.080	9.000	11.035	4.700	11.700	7.000
P24	Elbow Angle, with Steering	140.850	16.259	120.550	138.500	169.100	112.000	171.000	59.000
P25	Elbow Angle with Gear	142.600	12.262	124.550	146.500	155.350	116.000	162.000	46.000
P26	Right Knee - Dashboard	15.465	4.864	7.485	17.000	21.100	7.200	23.000	15.800
P27	Left Knee - Dashboard	16.300	2.929	12.985	16.000	20.200	12.700	24.000	11.300
P28	Knee Angle foot on Floor	127.300	14.669	106.450	129.500	151.000	96.000	151.000	55.000
P29	Ankle Angle foot on Pedal	120.100	15.921	95.800	124.500	142.200	92.000	146.000	54.000
P30	Back Angle Sitting	119.750	8.693	104.900	118.500	129.150	103.000	132.000	29.000

Table 2 presents a summarized statistical analysis of 30 parameters related to the anthropometric body dimensions of 20 male bus drivers employed by New Librando Transit Inc. bus company. The table includes measures such as mean, standard deviation, 5th, 50th, and 95th percentiles, minimum and maximum values, and range of anthropometric data collected during fieldwork. Mean values represent the central tendency of the dataset (Hurley & Tenny, 2023), while standard deviation indicates data variability and distribution (Omda & Sergent, 2023). Percentiles are

widely used in anthropometry to categorize anthropometric dimensions into alpha sizes (small, medium, large), aiding in understanding body size distribution (Zhang et al., 2016). These metrics are crucial for assessing whether bus driver cabin and seat dimensions adequately accommodate drivers' anthropometric data and driving posture for optimal performance. Additionally, minimum and maximum values signify the smallest and largest recorded values among respondents, with the range indicating the variation between these extremes for each anthropometric parameter.

The analysis of 30 key body measurements, including weight, sitting height, shoulder width, sitting eye height, head dimensions, arm and leg lengths, and other relevant dimensions, reveals significant variability among drivers, which has important implications for ergonomic design. The average weight of the respondents is 68.85 kg, ranging from 50 to 86 kg, indicating variability in body mass which could influence seat and steering positioning. The mean sitting height is 82.55 cm, with a range of 76 to 89 cm, highlighting variations in upper body height crucial for head and eye-level alignment with mirrors and the windshield. Sitting eye height, essential for determining drivers' ability to see the road and dashboard clearly, averages 70.05 cm, ranging from 62.4 to 79 cm. Shoulder width averages 43.51 cm, ranging from 39 to 50.8 cm, impacting seat width and lateral space for comfort during long driving periods. Additionally, shoulder height averages 53.1 cm, affecting armrest positioning and backrest height. Other key dimensions include shoulder-elbow length (34.67 cm), elbow-wrist length (27.35 cm), hand length (18.42 cm), knee height (53.86 cm), and foot length (27.56 cm), which play a critical role in determining body posture and the accessibility of controls. This information is crucial for assessing whether the current workspace setup optimally fits the drivers, potentially influencing their posture and overall comfort during long driving hours.

RESPONDENT'S RULA EMPLOYEE ASSESSMENT WORKSHEET

This section focuses on analyzing the RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet completed by each respondent, and to evaluate whether they exhibited optimal or improper postures during their 3-hour trip in South Cebu. The findings of the statistical analysis conducted are presented in this section.

Figure 12. *RULA Score of bus drivers*

Figure 12 provides a summary of respondents' RULA employee assessment worksheets, categorizing them into four classifications of RULA Scores that signify the risk level associated with task performance and driving posture during a 3-hour trip in South Cebu. Higher RULA Scores indicate an increased risk of developing musculoskeletal injuries (Bowden, 2018; Diego-Mas, 2023). The figure shows that 70 percent of respondents had RULA Scores of 5-6 (Action level 3), indicating a poor or improper driving posture with a risk of injury. This needs to be investigated and changed soon to prevent an injury. A driving posture with a RULA score of 5-6, which is signified as Action Level 3, will be illustrated in Figures 13, 14, 15, and 16, respectively. These will further enhance the understanding of the concept of the RULA

employee assessment worksheet and the importance of proper or improper postures in a workplace. Furthermore, 30 percent of respondents had scores of 7 and above (Action level 4), reflecting a worse posture with an immediate risk of injury. This necessitates investigation and changes immediately. Figures 17 and 18 illustrate the driving posture of other bus driver and their RULA employee assessment worksheet, earning a RULA score of 7 and above, which signified as Action Level 4. These findings align with the existing literature of Gogging et al. (2022), Majid et al. (2018), and Yasobant et al., (2015) highlighting transportation as having high rates of work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WRMSDs) impacting the joints, muscles, and tendons, ligaments, nerves, etc. Notably, none of the respondents had RULA Scores in the lower categories (1-2 and 3-4), indicating a lack of optimal or low-risk postures among the sampled bus drivers.

Figure 13. *Driving Posture of Respondent 1*

RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Complete this worksheet following the step-by-step procedure below. Keep a copy in the employee's personnel folder for future reference.

A. Arm & Wrist Analysis

Step 1: Locate Upper Arm Position

Step 1a: Adjust...

Final Upper Arm Score = 1

Step 2: Locate Lower Arm Position

Step 2a: Adjust...

Final Lower Arm Score = 2

Step 3: Locate Wrist Position

Step 3a: Adjust...

Final Wrist Score = 3

Step 4: Wrist Twist

Wrist Twist Score = 1

Step 5: Look-up Posture Score in Table A

Posture Score A = 3

Step 6: Add Muscle Use Score

Muscle Use Score = 1

Step 7: Add Force/load Score

Force/load Score = 2

Step 8: Find Row in Table C

Final Wrist & Arm Score = 6

SCORES

Table A

Upper Arm	Lower Arm	Wrist	Wrist Twist	
1	1	1	1	1
1	1	2	1	2
1	1	3	1	3
1	2	1	1	2
1	2	2	1	3
1	2	3	1	4
1	3	1	1	3
1	3	2	1	4
1	3	3	1	5
2	1	1	1	2
2	1	2	1	3
2	1	3	1	4
2	2	1	1	3
2	2	2	1	4
2	2	3	1	5
2	3	1	1	4
2	3	2	1	5
2	3	3	1	6
3	1	1	1	3
3	1	2	1	4
3	1	3	1	5
3	2	1	1	4
3	2	2	1	5
3	2	3	1	6
3	3	1	1	5
3	3	2	1	6
3	3	3	1	7

Table B

Neck	Trunk	Legs	
1	1	1	1
1	1	2	2
1	1	3	3
1	2	1	2
1	2	2	3
1	2	3	4
1	3	1	3
1	3	2	4
1	3	3	5
2	1	1	2
2	1	2	3
2	1	3	4
2	2	1	3
2	2	2	4
2	2	3	5
2	3	1	4
2	3	2	5
2	3	3	6
3	1	1	3
3	1	2	4
3	1	3	5
3	2	1	4
3	2	2	5
3	2	3	6
3	3	1	5
3	3	2	6
3	3	3	7

Table C

Wrist & Arm	Neck	Trunk	Legs
1	1	1	1
1	1	2	2
1	1	3	3
1	2	1	2
1	2	2	3
1	2	3	4
1	3	1	3
1	3	2	4
1	3	3	5
2	1	1	2
2	1	2	3
2	1	3	4
2	2	1	3
2	2	2	4
2	2	3	5
2	3	1	4
2	3	2	5
2	3	3	6
3	1	1	3
3	1	2	4
3	1	3	5
3	2	1	4
3	2	2	5
3	2	3	6
3	3	1	5
3	3	2	6
3	3	3	7

B. Neck, Trunk & Leg Analysis

Step 9: Locate Neck Position

Step 9a: Adjust...

Final Neck Score = 2

Step 10: Locate Trunk Position

Step 10a: Adjust...

Final Trunk Score = 2

Step 11: Legs

Final Leg Score = 1

Step 12: Look-up Posture Score in Table B

Posture B Score = 2

Step 13: Add Muscle Use Score

Muscle Use Score = 1

Step 14: Add Force/load Score

Force/load Score = 2

Step 15: Find Column in Table C

Final Neck, Trunk & Leg Score = 5

Final Score = 6

Subject: Driving Posture - R1 Date: 03/03/2024
 Company: New Librando Transit Inc. Department: Operations Department Scorer: BSIE 2023-2024 Researchers

FINAL SCORE: 1 or 2 = Acceptable; 3 or 4 investigate further; 5 or 6 investigate further and change soon; 7 investigate and change immediately

Source: McAtamney, L. & Corlett, E.N. (1993) RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders, Applied Ergonomics, 24(2) 91-99.
 © Professor Alan Hedge, Cornell University, Feb. 2001

Figure 14. RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet of Respondent 1

In Figures 13 and 14, the RULA assessment of one of the driver respondents during the 3-hour trip within South Cebu reveals moderate ergonomic risks due to the driver's posture. In the arm and wrist analysis, the upper arm is positioned neutrally with a score of 1 and an angle of +20° to 45°, indicating a relaxed posture. However, the lower arm shows mild flexion with a score of 2 and an angle between -60° to 100°, and the wrist is in a somewhat awkward position, scoring 3 with an angle between 0° to 15°, suggesting potential strain if maintained over time. Additionally, minimal wrist twisting was observed, with a score of 1. This hand position seems to be aligned with natural movements, so this isn't a major concern. The overall posture score for the arms and wrists is 6, indicating moderate risk, particularly due to the wrist's angle and

sustained grip on the steering wheel. In the neck, trunk, and leg analysis, the neck is slightly inclined, earning a score of 2 and an angle between 10° to 20° . This posture can cause discomfort if sustained, especially if the driver frequently looks down or leans forward while driving. The trunk also shows mild forward leaning with a score of 2 and an angle of 0° to 20° . However, prolonged periods in this posture might cause discomfort or lower back pain. The legs are in a neutral posture with a score of 1, suggesting little significant risk. Overall, the posture score for this area totals 5, which points to a potential moderate risk of discomfort, especially in the neck and trunk, if the position is held for extended periods. The total RULA score of 6 (Arm & Wrist: 6; Neck, Trunk & Leg: 5) suggests that while the driver's posture is not severely problematic, there are areas of moderate concern. The wrist position and lower arm bending could lead to strain over long hours of driving. The assessment highlights areas where the driver's posture could be improved, particularly the wrist and arm positions, to reduce the risk of musculoskeletal strain over long drives.

Figure 15. *Driving Posture of Respondent 2*

RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Complete this worksheet following the step-by-step procedure below. Keep a copy in the employee's personnel folder for future reference.

A. Arm & Wrist Analysis

Step 1: Locate Upper Arm Position
Step 1a: Adjust...
 If shoulder is raised: +1;
 If upper arm is abducted: +1;
 If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1
 Final Upper Arm Score = 2

Step 2: Locate Lower Arm Position
Step 2a: Adjust...
 If arm is working across midline of the body: +1;
 If arm out to side of body: +1
 Final Lower Arm Score = 2

Step 3: Locate Wrist Position
Step 3a: Adjust...
 If wrist is bent from the midline: +1
 Final Wrist Score = 3

Step 4: Wrist Twist
 If wrist is twisted mainly in mid-range = 1;
 If twist at or near end of twisting range = 2
 Wrist Twist Score = 2

Step 5: Look-up Posture Score in Table A
 Use values from steps 1, 2, 3 & 4 to locate Posture Score in Table A.
 Posture Score A = 4

Step 6: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static (i.e. held for longer than 1 minute) or:
 If action repeatedly occurs 4 times per minute or more: +1
 Muscle Use Score = 1

Step 7: Add Force/load Score
 If load less than 2 kg (intermittent): +0;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (intermittent): +1;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (static or repeated): +2;
 If more than 10 kg load or repeated or shocks: +3
 Force/load Score = 2

Step 8: Find Row in Table C
 The completed score from the Arm/Wrist analysis is used to find the row on Table C.
 Final Wrist & Arm Score = 7

SCORES

Table A

Upper	Lower	Wrist	Twist	Force	Muscle
1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	1	2	1	1
1	1	1	3	1	1
1	1	2	1	1	1
1	1	2	2	1	1
1	1	2	3	1	1
1	2	1	1	1	1
1	2	1	2	1	1
1	2	1	3	1	1
1	2	2	1	1	1
1	2	2	2	1	1
1	2	2	3	1	1
1	3	1	1	1	1
1	3	1	2	1	1
1	3	1	3	1	1
1	3	2	1	1	1
1	3	2	2	1	1
1	3	2	3	1	1
2	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	2	1	1
2	1	1	3	1	1
2	1	2	1	1	1
2	1	2	2	1	1
2	1	2	3	1	1
2	2	1	1	1	1
2	2	1	2	1	1
2	2	1	3	1	1
2	2	2	1	1	1
2	2	2	2	1	1
2	2	2	3	1	1
2	3	1	1	1	1
2	3	1	2	1	1
2	3	1	3	1	1
2	3	2	1	1	1
2	3	2	2	1	1
2	3	2	3	1	1
3	1	1	1	1	1
3	1	1	2	1	1
3	1	1	3	1	1
3	1	2	1	1	1
3	1	2	2	1	1
3	1	2	3	1	1
3	2	1	1	1	1
3	2	1	2	1	1
3	2	1	3	1	1
3	2	2	1	1	1
3	2	2	2	1	1
3	2	2	3	1	1
3	3	1	1	1	1
3	3	1	2	1	1
3	3	1	3	1	1
3	3	2	1	1	1
3	3	2	2	1	1
3	3	2	3	1	1

Table B

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Neck	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Legs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Trunk	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Neck	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Legs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Trunk	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Neck	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Legs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Trunk	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Table C

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
3	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
4	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
5	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
6	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
7	7	8	9	10	11	12	13

B. Neck, Trunk & Leg Analysis

Step 9: Locate Neck Position
Step 9a: Adjust...
 If neck is tilted: +1; if neck is side-bending: +1
 Final Neck Score = 2

Step 10: Locate Trunk Position
Step 10a: Adjust...
 If trunk is tilted: +1; if trunk is side-bending: +1
 Final Trunk Score = 2

Step 11: Legs
 If legs & feet supported and balanced: +1;
 If not: +2
 Final Leg Score = 1

Step 12: Look-up Posture Score in Table B
 Use values from steps 9, 10 & 11 to locate Posture Score in Table B.
 Posture B Score = 2

Step 13: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static or:
 If action: 4 minutes or more: +1
 Muscle Use Score = 1

Step 14: Add Force/load Score
 If load is less than 2 kg (intermittent): +0;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (intermittent): +1;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (static or repeated): +2;
 If more than 10 kg load or repeated or shocks: +3
 Force/load Score = 2

Step 15: Find Column in Table C
 The completed score from the Neck/Trunk & Leg analysis is used to find the column on Chart C.
 Final Neck, Trunk & Leg Score = 5

Subject: Driving Posture - R2 Date: 03/10/2024
 Company: New Librando Transit Inc. Department: Operations Department Scorer: BSIE 2023-2024 Researcher

Final Score = 7

FINAL SCORE: 1 or 2 = Acceptable; 3 or 4 investigate further; 5 or 6 investigate further and change soon; 7 investigate and change immediately

Source: McAtamney, L. & Corlett, E.N. (1993) RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders. *Applied Ergonomics*, 24(2) 91-99.
 © Professor Alan Hedge, Cornell University, Feb. 2001

Figure 16. RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet of Respondent 2

Figures 15 and 16 provide another illustration of the driving posture of another respondent and their RULA employee assessment worksheet. The RULA assessment of the driver reveals moderate ergonomic risks, particularly in the arm and wrist positions. The upper arm score of 2 and an angle between +20° to 45° suggests that it is slightly elevated, and the lower arm, scoring 2, is bent within a normal range of -60° to 100° angle, though prolonged bending could lead to discomfort. The wrist, however, deviates from the neutral position with a score of 3 and an angle between 0° to 15°, and the wrist twist scored at 2, adding further risk over long periods. The overall posture for the arm and wrist yields a score of 7, highlighting a moderate risk for musculoskeletal issues, particularly due to the prolonged driving posture. In the neck, trunk, and leg analysis, the neck shows a slight forward tilt from 10° to 20° angle with

a score of 2, common in driving but can lead to tension or pain, while the trunk is also slightly leaned backward from 0° to 20° angle, scoring 2, indicating a posture that could become uncomfortable over extended periods. The legs are positioned neutrally with a score of 1, posing little risk. The overall score for this area is 5, indicating moderate risk, especially in the neck and trunk areas, which may cause discomfort during extended periods of driving. The driver's arm and wrist positions present the highest concern, with moderate scores suggesting the potential for discomfort or injury over time. The assessment suggests that the driver could benefit from ergonomic adjustments to achieve more neutral arm and wrist postures, as well as periodic breaks to reduce tension in the neck and trunk.

Figure 17. *Driving Posture of Respondent 3*

RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Complete this worksheet following the step-by-step procedure below. Keep a copy in the employee's personnel folder for future reference.

A. Arm & Wrist Analysis

Step 1: Locate Upper Arm Position

Step 1a: Adjust...
 If shoulder is raised: +1;
 If upper arm is abducted: +1;
 If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1
 Final Upper Arm Score = 2

Step 2: Locate Lower Arm Position

Step 2a: Adjust...
 If arm is working across midline of the body: +1;
 If arm out to side of body: +1
 Final Lower Arm Score = 3

Step 3: Locate Wrist Position

Step 3a: Adjust...
 If wrist is bent from the midline: +1
 Final Wrist Score = 3

Step 4: Wrist Twist
 If wrist is twisted mainly in mid-range = 1;
 If twist at or near end of twisting range = 2
 Wrist Twist Score = 1

Step 5: Look-up Posture Score in Table A
 Use values from steps 1, 2, 3 & 4 to locate Posture Score in Table A.
 Posture Score A = 4

Step 6: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static (i.e. held for longer than 1 minute) or:
 If action repeatedly occurs 4 times per minute or more: +1
 Muscle Use Score = 1

Step 7: Add Force/load Score
 If load less than 2 kg (intermittent): +0;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (intermittent): +1;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (static or repeated): +2;
 If more than 10 kg load or repeated or shocks: +3
 Force/load Score = 2

Step 8: Find Row in Table C
 The completed score from the Arm/wrist analysis is used to find the row on Table C.
 Final Wrist & Arm Score = 7

SCORES

Table A

Upper Arm	Lower Arm	Wrist	Wrist Twist	Posture Score
1	1	1	1	1
1	1	2	1	2
1	1	3	1	3
1	2	1	1	4
1	2	2	1	5
1	2	3	1	6
1	3	1	1	7
1	3	2	1	8
1	3	3	1	9
2	1	1	1	10
2	1	2	1	11
2	1	3	1	12
2	2	1	1	13
2	2	2	1	14
2	2	3	1	15
2	3	1	1	16
2	3	2	1	17
2	3	3	1	18
3	1	1	1	19
3	1	2	1	20
3	1	3	1	21
3	2	1	1	22
3	2	2	1	23
3	2	3	1	24
3	3	1	1	25
3	3	2	1	26
3	3	3	1	27

Table B

Neck	Legs		Legs		Legs	
	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	1	2	1	1	1	1
1	1	3	1	1	1	1
1	2	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	2	1	1	1	1
1	2	3	1	1	1	1
1	3	1	1	1	1	1
1	3	2	1	1	1	1
1	3	3	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	2	1	1	1	1
2	1	3	1	1	1	1
2	2	1	1	1	1	1
2	2	2	1	1	1	1
2	2	3	1	1	1	1
2	3	1	1	1	1	1
2	3	2	1	1	1	1
2	3	3	1	1	1	1
3	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	1	2	1	1	1	1
3	1	3	1	1	1	1
3	2	1	1	1	1	1
3	2	2	1	1	1	1
3	2	3	1	1	1	1
3	3	1	1	1	1	1
3	3	2	1	1	1	1
3	3	3	1	1	1	1

Table C

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	2	1	1	1	1	1
1	3	1	1	1	1	1
1	4	1	1	1	1	1
1	5	1	1	1	1	1
1	6	1	1	1	1	1
1	7	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	2	1	1	1	1	1
2	3	1	1	1	1	1
2	4	1	1	1	1	1
2	5	1	1	1	1	1
2	6	1	1	1	1	1
2	7	1	1	1	1	1
3	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	2	1	1	1	1	1
3	3	1	1	1	1	1
3	4	1	1	1	1	1
3	5	1	1	1	1	1
3	6	1	1	1	1	1
3	7	1	1	1	1	1

Final Score = 7

B. Neck, Trunk & Leg Analysis

Step 9: Locate Neck Position

Step 9a: Adjust...
 If neck is twisted: +1; If neck is side-bending: +1
 Final Neck Score = 3

Step 10: Locate Trunk Position

Step 10a: Adjust...
 If trunk is twisted: +1; If trunk is side-bending: +1
 Final Trunk Score = 3

Step 11: Legs
 If legs & feet supported and balanced: +1;
 If not: +2
 Final Leg Score = 1

Step 12: Look-up Posture Score in Table B
 Use values from steps 9, 10 & 11 to locate Posture Score in Table B.
 Posture B Score = 4

Step 13: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static or:
 If action 4 times or more: +1
 Muscle Use Score = 1

Step 14: Add Force/load Score
 If load less than 2 kg (intermittent): +0;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (intermittent): +1;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (static or repeated): +2;
 If more than 10 kg load or repeated or shocks: +3
 Force/load Score = 2

Step 15: Find Column in Table C
 The completed score from the Neck/Trunk & Leg analysis is used to find the column on Chart C.
 Final Neck, Trunk & Leg Score = 7

Subject: Driving Posture - R3 Date: 03/03/2024
 Company: New Librando Transit Inc. Department: Operations Department Scorer: BSIE 2023-2024 Researcher

FINAL SCORE: 1 or 2 = Acceptable; 3 or 4 investigate further; 5 or 6 investigate further and change soon; 7 investigate and change immediately
Source: McAtamney, L. & Corlett, E.N. (1993) RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders. Applied Ergonomics, 24(2) 91-99.
 © Professor Alan Hedge, Cornell University, Feb. 2001

Figure 18. RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet of Respondent 3

Figures 17 and 18, as presented above, illustrate the driving posture and RULA assessment for the driver earning a RULA score of 7 and above (Action Level 4). The assessment indicates significant ergonomic risks due to poor posture. In the arm and wrist analysis, the upper arm scores 2 with an angle between $+20^\circ$ to 45° , suggesting it is slightly raised, while the lower arm scores 3, reflecting an angle beyond 100° , which indicates discomfort over time. The wrist is also in a non-neutral position, scoring 3, which reflects an angle between 0° to 15° , and wrist twisting is minimal with a score of 1. The wrist position, combined with prolonged use, suggests potential strain. The overall posture score for the arms and wrists is 7, highlighting moderate to high risk for musculoskeletal issues. In the neck, trunk, and leg analysis, the neck shows significant forward bending from 10° to 20° angle, earning a score of 3, which indicates

an increased risk for strain. The trunk is similarly bent forward from an angle of 20° to 60°, with a score of 3, and although the legs are in a neutral posture with a score of 1, the combined posture score for this area is 7, suggesting a higher risk of musculoskeletal discomfort, particularly in the neck and trunk. Overall, the assessment shows that the driver is at moderate to high ergonomic risk, with particular concern for the lower arms, wrists, neck, and trunk.

The assessment highlights areas where the driver's posture could be improved to reduce the risk of musculoskeletal strain over long drives. Taking regular breaks may help alleviate some of these concerns, relieve strain, and reduce the likelihood of discomfort or injury.

RESPONDENT'S BUS DRIVER CABIN AND BUS DRIVER SEAT

This section deals with the dimensions of the bus driver cabin and bus driver seat used by the respective respondents.

Table 3. Summary of data obtained from New Librando Transit Inc. bus driver cabin.

P. No.	Bus Driver Cabin Dimensions	Mean (cm)	Standard Deviation (cm)	5 th Percentile (cm)	50 th Percentile (cm)	95 th Percentile (cm)
P2.1	Cabin Height	183.950	18.851	165.000	177.500	213.000
P2.2	Cabin Width	215.800	23.303	205.850	216.000	235.100
P2.3	Cabin Length	135.200	16.069	117.750	132.750	159.050
P2.4	Seat to Floor distance	35.925	6.650	26.000	38.000	45.000
P2.5	Pedal to Seat distance	37.550	3.517	29.000	38.000	41.000
P2.6	Steering to Floor	64.700	3.092	58.000	67.000	67.000
P2.7	Dashboard-Backrest distance	86.400	4.012	80.500	87.000	90.100
P2.8	Steering to Backrest distance	47.350	10.080	31.000	52.500	56.300
P2.9	Steering wheel external diameter	39.100	1.924	36.000	39.500	41.000
P2.10	Steering rim thickness	5.635	3.036	3.600	4.500	11.500
P2.11	Pedal Angle	121.050	17.739	100.000	120.000	140.000
P2.12	Dashboard to Seat distance	29.400	3.382	25.475	30.000	33.050
P2.13	Gear lever to Seat distance	14.833	4.876	7.000	15.000	23.200

Table 4. Summary of data obtained from New Librando Transit Inc. bus driver seat

P.No.	Bus Driver Seat Dimensions	Mean (cm)	Standard Deviation (cm)	5 th Percentile (cm)	50 th Percentile (cm)	95 th Percentile (cm)
P3.1	Seat Overall Height	108.15	6.53	99.60	109.00	114.70
P3.2	Total Seatback Height	88.58	7.87	78.30	90.50	97.50
P3.3	Seat Height	42.60	3.29	38.00	45.00	46.00
P3.4	Seatpan Thickness	12.58	3.64	7.00	13.50	16.50
P3.5	Seat Width	54.20	1.90	51.00	54.00	57.00
P3.6	Seat Depth	48.60	5.09	44.00	47.00	57.53
P3.7	Backrest Angle	101.75	5.78	92.00	105.00	105.00
P3.8	Backrest Thickness	51.95	3.27	47.00	52.50	56.00
P3.9	Backrest Width (Lumbar level)	16.82	2.70	13.88	17.75	20.00
P3.10	Backrest Width (Shoulder level)	11.98	2.50	9.00	11.00	15.50
P3.11	Backrest Height	74.53	7.91	66.93	75.00	84.00
P3.12	Headrest Angle	101.98	14.25	94.75	99.00	130.23
P3.13	Headrest Width	30.73	7.99	25.00	27.00	45.00
P3.14	Headrest Height (with stand)	14.50	5.01	7.00	17.00	18.50
P3.15	Headrest Height (no stand)	14.05	6.68	5.00	18.00	22.00

Tables 3 and 4 present a summarized statistical analysis of 13 parameters for bus driver cabin dimensions and 15 parameters for bus driver seat dimensions, respectively, based on the vehicles used by respondents from New Librando Transit Inc. transportation company. The analysis includes measures such as mean, standard

deviation, and percentiles (5th, 50th, and 95th) of data obtained during fieldwork. Percentiles, widely utilized in anthropometry, categorize measurements into small, medium, and large dimensions, denoted as alpha sizes (Zhang et al., 2016). These metrics aid in understanding the range of object sizes and assessing whether they fall within typical ranges. The purpose is to evaluate the alignment of bus drivers' anthropometric measurements and their driving posture within the workspace, ensuring it promotes physical, functional, and psychological comfort for users.

Bus Driver Cabin

The analysis of the bus driver cabin includes measurements such as cabin height, width, and length. The average height of the cabin is 183.95 cm, its width is 215.8 cm, and its length is 135.2 cm. Other dimensions include the distance from the seat to the floor, from the pedal to the seat, and from the steering wheel to the floor. Seat-to-floor distance averages 35.925 cm, pedal-to-seat distance averages 37.55 cm, and steering-wheel-to-floor distance averages 64.7 cm. These measurements help evaluate how well the space accommodates the drivers based on their anthropometric data, which is essential for promoting ergonomic safety and comfort during long driving periods. For instance, the distance from the dashboard to the backrest, with a mean of 86.4 cm, and the steering wheel to the backrest, with a mean of 47.350 cm, are imperative in determining whether the driver can maintain a safe and comfortable posture.

Bus Driver Seat

Similarly, the bus driver seat dimensions are vital for assessing comfort and posture. These include measurements like seat height, width, depth, and the backrest's angle and thickness. The mean seating height is 42.6 cm, the width is 54.2 cm, the depth is 48.6 cm, and the backrest's angle is 101.75°, while the backrest's

thickness is 51.95 cm. The analysis also measures specific parts such as the lumbar and shoulder-level backrest widths, headrest height, and angle. Lumbar and shoulder-level backrest widths average 16.82 cm and 11.98 cm, respectively. Headrest height averages 14.5 cm with a stand, and 14.05 cm is the mean average headrest height with no stand. Additionally, the headrest angle averages 101.98°. The data reflects the importance of seat adjustability and support for the drivers, as proper seat dimensions can prevent musculoskeletal strain, especially during prolonged driving.

These analyses are significant as they help to assess whether the cabin and seat dimensions align with the drivers' anthropometric measurements and their driving posture, ensuring that the driving environment is both functional and ergonomic.

SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN VARIABLES

This section deals with the significant relationship between anthropometric body measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of bus driver cabins and seats of New Librando Transit Inc. buses. Specifically, this section was structured into two subsections: first, to identify the significant relationships between anthropometric body measurements and bus driver cabin as shown in Table 5; and second, as outlined in Table 6, to identify the significant relationship between the anthropometric body measurements of bus drivers and bus driver seat.

Table 5. Test of a significant relationship between anthropometric body measurements and bus driver cabin

Predictor		Coefficients ^a				
		Estimate	SE	t	p	Stand. Estimate
1	Sitting Height	0.939	1.3	0.725	0.478	0.168
	Sitting Eye Height	0.14	0.212	0.658	0.519	0.153
	Shoulder Width	2.49	1.43	1.750	0.097	0.381
	Shoulder Height	1.61	0.918	1.758	0.096	0.383
	Head Length	2.46	5.11	0.483	0.635	0.113
	Head Breadth	0.316	0.421	0.751	0.462	0.174
	Shoulder - Elbow Length	-1.13	0.721	-1.570	0.135	-0.346
	Elbow - Wrist Length	-0.919	0.783	-1.170	0.256	-0.267
	Hand Length & Hand Breadth	-0.624	0.426	-1.460	0.16	-0.326
	Elbow Rest Height	0.389	0.464	0.838	0.413	0.194
	Knee Height	0.205	0.278	0.738	0.47	0.171
	Buttock - Knee Length	0.218	0.191	1.140	0.27	0.259
	Buttock - Popliteal Length	0.236	0.195	1.210	0.242	0.274
	Popliteal Height	-0.362	0.184	-1.970	0.065	-0.421
	Hip Breadth	2.52	2.36	1.070	0.3	0.244
	Thigh - Clearance Height	-0.0408	0.22	-0.185	0.855	-0.0436
	Abdominal Depth	-0.066	0.191	-0.345	0.734	-0.081
	Abdominal - Steering	-1.47	0.573	2.560	0.02	0.516
	Chest - Steering	0.0492	0.271	0.181	0.858	0.0427
	Foot Length	0.165	1.87	0.088	0.931	0.0208
	Elbow Angle with Steering	-0.0705	0.145	-0.485	0.633	-0.114
	Elbow Angle with Gear	-0.178	0.0704	-2.530	0.021	-0.512
	Right Knee - Dashboard	-0.0389	0.164	-0.238	0.815	-0.0559
	Left Knee - Dashboard	-0.107	0.271	-0.395	0.697	-0.0927
	Knee Angle (Foot on Floor)	0.0211	0.107	0.120	0.845	0.0466
	Ankle Angle (Foot on Pedal)	-0.192	0.259	-0.743	0.467	-0.173
	Back Angle Sitting	0.0792	0.273	0.291	0.775	0.0683

a. Dependent Variable: **Bus Driver Cabin***

<i>*Bus Driver Cabin</i>	
P.No.	Bus Driver Cabin Dimensions
P2.1	Cabin Height
P2.12	Dashboard to Seat
P2.2	Cabin Width
P2.8	Steering to Backrest
P2.9	Steering Wheel External Diameter
P2.10	Steering Rim Thickness
P2.5	Pedal to Seat
P2.4	Seat to Floor
P2.6	Steering to Floor
P2.11	Pedal Angle
P3.13	Gear Lever to Seat

Table 5 explores the relationships between various anthropometric body measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of the bus driver cabin. Anthropometric body measurements were used to assess ergonomic fit, comfort, or suitability of workspace for individuals based on their physical dimensions (Marshall & Summerskill, 2019), which have a substantial impact on their driving posture. The objective of the analysis is to understand how drivers' physical characteristics influence their interaction with the bus driver cabin, focusing on ergonomic fit and comfort. The bus driver's cabin is treated as the dependent variable, which includes cabin height, dashboard-to-seat distance, cabin width, steering-to-backrest distance, pedal-to-seat distance, pedal angle, and more, as shown below in Table 5. Whereas the predictor variables include a range of body measurements such as sitting height, sitting eye height, shoulder width, elbow-wrist length, knee height, foot length, and more.

The analysis presents coefficients for each body measurement, which reflect the strength and direction of the relationship with the cabin dimensions. These coefficients, along with t-values and p-values, help determine whether the relationships are statistically significant, with a p-value below 0.05 being considered significant (Zuo et al., 2003; Marill, 2008). The standardized estimates further indicate

the magnitude of the relationship in standardized terms, allowing for comparisons across the different variables (Eberly, 2007).

A few key significant relationships were observed. The abdominal depth-to-steering distance showed a statistically significant negative relationship ($p = 0.02$), with a coefficient estimate of -1.47. This suggests that as abdominal depth increases, the distance between the abdomen and the steering wheel decreases, potentially influencing the driver's comfort and control. Another significant finding was the elbow angle with gear, which also demonstrated a significant relationship ($p = 0.021$) with a negative estimate (-0.178). This indicates that as the elbow angle changes, the ergonomic fit between the driver and the gear system is affected.

In contrast, the majority of the other body measurements did not show significant relationships with the cabin dimensions. For example, sitting height ($p = 0.478$), foot length ($p = 0.931$), and knee height ($p = 0.47$) all had p-values well above the threshold for significance, indicating that these measurements do not have a substantial impact on the ergonomic relationship between the bus driver and the cabin. Measurements such as shoulder width and head length similarly showed non-significant results, as reflected by p-values of 0.097 and 0.635, respectively. These non-significant results suggest that, for many body dimensions, there is no clear relationship with the cabin setup that would affect driver posture or comfort.

Overall, the findings from Table 5 highlight that only a few specific anthropometric measurements, such as abdominal depth and elbow angle, play a significant role in shaping the ergonomic dynamics of the bus driver cabin. In contrast, most other body measurements do not appear to significantly influence the relationship between the driver and the cabin's dimensions.

Table 6. Test of a significant relationship between anthropometric body measurements and bus driver seat

Predictor	Coefficients ^a					
	Estimate	SE	t	p	Stand. Estimate	
1	Sitting Height	-0.32	0.543	-0.589	0.563	-0.137
	Popliteal Height	-0.00634	0.0729	-0.087	0.932	-0.0205
	Sitting Eye Height	-0.261	0.499	-0.523	0.607	-0.122
	Shoulder Width	0.0144	0.125	0.115	0.91	0.027
	Shoulder Height	-0.697	0.762	-0.915	0.372	-0.211
	Knee Height	0.165	0.406	0.407	0.689	0.0955
	Buttock-Knee Length	-0.521	0.257	-2.030	0.058	-0.431
	Buttock-Popliteal Length	-0.339	0.295	-1.150	0.265	-0.261
	Thigh-Clearance Height	0.518	0.422	1.230	0.235	0.278
	Elbow-Wrist Length	-0.393	0.278	-1.410	0.175	-0.316
	Shoulder-Elbow Length	0.15	0.602	0.249	0.806	0.0586
	Head Length	-0.592	1.36	-0.436	0.668	-0.102
	Abdominal Depth	-0.469	0.309	-1.520	0.146	-0.337
	Knee Angle (Foot on Floor)	0.0532	0.0513	1.040	0.314	0.237
	Back Angle Sitting	-0.0838	0.155	-0.539	0.596	-0.126
	Head Breadth	-2.75	1.61	-1.71	0.105	-0.373

a. Dependent Variable: **Bus Driver Seat***

<i>*Bus Driver Seat</i>	
P.No.	Bus Driver Seat Dimensions
P3.2	Total Seatback Height
P3.3	Seat Height
P3.11	Backrest Height
P3.5	Seat Width
P3.6	Seat Depth
P3.4	Seatpan Thickness
P3.7	Backrest Angle
P3.14	Headrest Height (with stand)
P3.13	Headrest Width

Table 6 examines the significant relationships between the anthropometric body measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of the bus driver seat. The goal is to assess how different body measurements affect the ergonomics and comfort of the seat. The bus driver seat is the dependent variable, which covers the total seatback height, seat height, backrest height, seat width, seat depth, and more. On the other hand, the predictor variables comprise various body measurements such as sitting height, popliteal height, sitting eye height, shoulder width, knee height, and others.

In this analysis, a few notable findings emerge. Buttock-knee length approaches significance with a p-value of 0.058, and its negative coefficient (-0.521) suggests that as buttock-knee length increases, the ergonomic fit between the seat and the driver worsens. This implies that drivers with longer buttock-knee lengths may experience discomfort in their seating posture.

Most other body measurements, such as sitting height ($p = 0.563$), popliteal height ($p = 0.932$), and elbow-wrist length ($p = 0.175$), did not show significant relationships with the seat dimensions. This suggests that these particular measurements do not strongly influence the ergonomic fit or comfort level provided by the seat. Additionally, variables like shoulder width ($p = 0.91$) and shoulder height ($p = 0.372$) were also non-significant, indicating minimal impact on the seating posture.

In conclusion, while certain measurement like buttock-knee length show some potential impact on bus driver seat ergonomics, most other anthropometric variables examined in this table did not significantly affect the seat's fit. The results highlight that only specific dimensions may contribute to variations in seating comfort or posture, with many body measurements having little to no effect on the ergonomic relationship between the driver and the seat.

SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE BETWEEN VARIABLES

This section addresses the significant differences between the anthropometric measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of the bus driver cabins and seats, both categorized within the 95th percentile. It is divided into two parts: the first focuses on determining the significant difference between the anthropometric measurements and the dimensions of the bus driver cabin, both grouped at the 95th percentile, as presented in Table 7; the second, outlined in Table 8, examines the significant difference between the bus drivers' anthropometric measurements and the dimensions of the bus driver seat, also grouped at the 95th percentile.

Table 7. Test of significant difference between anthropometric body measurements and bus driver cabin

	<i>Anthropometric Body Dimensions (95th Percentile)</i>	<i>Bus Driver Cabin Dimensions (95th Percentile)</i>
Mean	59.76148148	70.61296296
Variance	2256.385	4420.246075
Observations	27	27
Pearson Correlation	-0.109171977	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	26	
t Stat	-0.656975956	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.258485056	
t Critical one-tail	1.70561792	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.516970113	
t Critical two-tail	2.055529439	

Table 7 presents the results of a t-test conducted to compare the anthropometric body measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of the bus driver cabin, both grouped at the 95th percentile. The use of the 95th percentile in this analysis is a standard practice in ergonomic and anthropometric studies (Fromuth & Parkinson, 2009). The 95th percentile ensures that the cabin and seat design can

accommodate a large majority of the population, particularly larger individuals (Openshaw et al., 2006), ensuring comfort, safety, and efficiency. If the cabin dimensions are too small for individuals in the higher percentiles, this could result in discomfort, awkward postures, and even chronic health issues (Ismaila et al., 2021), all of which can negatively impact driver performance and well-being.

The analysis aimed to determine if there was a statistically significant difference between the two sets of measurements. The results show that the mean of the anthropometric body measurements is 59.76 with a variance of 2256.385, while the mean of the bus driver cabin dimensions is 70.61 with a variance of 4420.246. The t-statistic of -0.657 and a two-tailed p-value of 0.517 indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the body measurements and cabin dimensions at the 95th percentile. As the p-value is greater than the standard significance level of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that any observed differences are likely due to random variation rather than an actual discrepancy in the design.

Table 8. Test of significant difference between anthropometric body measurements and bus driver seat

	<i>Anthropometric Body Dimensions (95th Percentile)</i>	<i>Bus Driver Seat Dimensions (95th Percentile)</i>
Mean	57.799375	66.630625
Variance	1435.180353	850.9739796
Observations	16	16
Pearson Correlation	0.286330078	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	15	
t Stat	-0.868774802	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.199329056	
t Critical one-tail	1.753050356	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.398658112	
t Critical two-tail	2.131449546	

Table 8 presents the results of a t-test that compares the anthropometric body measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of the bus driver seat, both grouped at the 95th percentile. The analysis aimed to determine whether there is a significant difference between the two sets of measurements, which is critical for ensuring that the seat design accommodates larger individuals within the 95th percentile. The anthropometric body dimensions had a mean of 57.80 with a variance of 1435.18, while the seat dimensions had a higher mean of 66.63 and a variance of 850.97, with 16 observations for each. The t-statistic of -0.869 and a two-tailed p-value of 0.399 indicate no statistically significant difference between the body measurements and seat dimensions. As the p-value is greater than the threshold of 0.05, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, suggesting that any observed variations are likely due to chance rather than a true mismatch between body size and seat dimensions. Therefore, conducting these analyses is essential for ensuring ergonomic seating that supports proper posture, reduces strain, and enhances operational efficiency (Ismaila et al., 2021).

CHAPTER 3

SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter contains the summary, findings, conclusions, and action plan of the study. Based on the series of specific problems found in Chapter 1, the findings are summarily presented in the following portion of this chapter.

SUMMARY

The transportation industry forms the backbone of modern society, connecting people, businesses, and communities across the globe with unparalleled convenience and efficiency in minimal time. Bus drivers play a pivotal role in navigating a complex network of routes ensuring the seamless flow of passengers and goods. Despite their crucial role, these dedicated professionals frequently endure suboptimal working postures. This can result in discomfort, health problems like work-related musculoskeletal disorders, and reduced job satisfaction.

The main objective of this study was to evaluate the working posture of 20 bus drivers aged 39-59 years, measuring their body anthropometric dimensions, and conducting an ergonomic evaluation of the bus driver cabins and bus driver seats, during the Academic Year 2023-2024. The findings of this study would be the basis for proposing an immediate action plan ensuring that the workplace is designed and maintained in such a way that it will continue to provide physical, functional, and psychological comfort for users. The researchers gathered data from bus drivers in terms of age, years of employment, medical history, and Body Mass Index (BMI). The researchers also look into the seriousness the problem encountered reflecting the working postures during daily operations; the significant relationships and significant differences between anthropometric measurements of bus drivers, and the

dimensions of bus driver cabins and bus driver seats; and coping with the problem and potential ergonomic interventions and strategies.

The study employed a quantitative type of research that collects and analyzed numerical data, and partnered with an observation, evaluation, and structured interview to gather data. Observations and evaluation were performed on the front seat beside the driver's seat of the bus to observed and evaluate driving posture. Assessment on the bus driver's body dimensions and bus driver cabins was conducted in their bus garage. The structured interview were given to the New Librando Transit Inc. manager in their respective office for collecting demographic profiles of bus drivers. The gathered data were treated in a statistical manner using the percentage, grand mean, standard deviation, range, percentiles (5th, 50th, and 95th percentiles), simple linear regression analysis, and t-test: Paired two sample for means, using Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet 2010 version and SPSS version 22. The insights gained from this research have the potential to inform policy decisions of the company, the occupational health and safety professionals, and the government and may shape future interventions.

FINDINGS

After the data were gathered, classified, tabulated, computed, analyzed, and interpreted, the following findings were drawn:

For the profile of respondents in terms of age, it was found that the majority of the respondents (35 percent) are predominantly composed of middle-aged individuals aged 39-43 years old. For the profile of respondents in terms of years of employment, it was found that 30 percent of the respondents have worked in their roles for 15-19 years, indicating considerable experience in the profession. In terms of medical

history, the study showed that out of the nine categories provided, all bus drivers surveyed showed no documented medical issues, indicating the fulfillment of the researchers' inclusion and exclusion criteria, thereby focusing the basis of the RULA score toward ergonomic factors. For the profile of respondents in terms of Body Mass Index, out of 4 categories, half of the respondents (50 percent) fall into the overweight category.

In Figure 13, the Respondent's RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet section presents findings on the driving postures of bus drivers over a 3-hour trip in South Cebu. The RULA (Rapid Upper Limb Assessment) tool was used to evaluate ergonomic risks, focusing on the neck, trunk, and upper limb positions. The results reveal that 70% of the respondents scored between 5-6 (Action Level 3), indicating postures that pose a moderate risk of injury due to poor positioning. This needs to be investigated and changed soon to prevent an injury. Specific areas of concern include the drivers' wrist angles, sustained arm flexion, and slight forward bending of the neck and trunk. While the arm and wrist positioning exhibited moderate ergonomic risks, poor trunk and neck postures may also contribute to potential strain if sustained. These findings support the need for ergonomic interventions, such as providing regular breaks, to mitigate risks and improve drivers' long-term comfort and safety.

Table 5 shows the section on analyzing the relationships between bus drivers' anthropometric body measurements and the dimensions of the bus driver cabins. Key findings reveal that certain body measurements, specifically abdominal depth-to-steering distance and elbow angle with gear, show statistically significant relationships with the cabin dimensions, with a p-value of 0.02 and 0.021 respectively. For instance, there is a significant negative correlation between abdominal depth and the distance from the abdomen to the steering wheel, indicating that as abdominal depth increases,

the available space decreases, potentially affecting driver comfort and control. Similarly, a significant relationship between the elbow angle and the gear system highlights that variations in this angle impact ergonomic fit and usability, underscoring the importance of this measurement in cabin design. On the other hand, most other measurements, such as sitting height ($p = 0.478$), foot length ($p = 0.931$), knee height ($p = 0.47$), shoulder width ($p = 0.097$), and head length ($p = 0.635$), show no significant correlation with cabin dimensions. This suggests that these measurements do not notably influence the ergonomic relationship between the driver and cabin setup, having little effect on posture and comfort. Overall, the analysis concludes that while abdominal depth and elbow angle are essential for ergonomic cabin design, the majority of body measurements do not significantly impact driver-cabin ergonomics.

Consequently, Table 6 examines the relationships between various anthropometric body measurements of bus drivers and the ergonomic dimensions of the bus driver seat. Noteworthy findings include a near-significant relationship between buttock-knee length and seat ergonomics, with a negative coefficient (-0.521) and a p-value of 0.058. This result suggests that as the buttock-knee length increases, the ergonomic fit between the seat and the driver becomes less optimal, potentially causing discomfort in posture. Other body measurements, such as sitting height ($p = 0.563$), popliteal height ($p = 0.932$), elbow-wrist length ($p = 0.175$), shoulder width ($p = 0.91$), and shoulder height ($p = 0.372$), showed no significant impact on seat fit or comfort, indicating limited influence of these measurements on the ergonomic alignment of the bus driver seat.

In the section analyzing the significant differences between anthropometric body measurements and bus driver cabin dimensions, as presented in Table 7, the study performed a t-test to compare these measurements at the 95th percentile. This

percentile ensures that the cabin design can accommodate a larger portion of drivers, especially those with larger dimensions. The results showed that the mean of the anthropometric measurements was 59.76, with a variance of 2256.39, whereas the mean of the cabin dimensions was higher at 70.61, with a variance of 4420.246. The analysis yielded a t-statistic of -0.657 and a two-tailed p-value of 0.517, indicating that there was no statistically significant difference between the anthropometric measurements and the cabin dimensions at the 95th percentile. This suggests that any observed variations were likely due to random differences rather than a true design discrepancy, supporting the hypothesis that the current cabin dimensions adequately fit the anthropometric requirements of the drivers in this percentile.

Following that, Table 8 explores the significant differences between anthropometric body measurements of bus drivers and the dimensions of the bus driver seat at the 95th percentile. The mean of the anthropometric body measurements was 57.80, with a variance of 1435.18, while the mean seat dimension was 66.63 with a variance of 850.97. The t-test results, with a t-statistic of -0.869 and a two-tailed p-value of 0.399, indicate no statistically significant difference between the body measurements and seat dimensions. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected, suggesting that observed differences may result from random variation rather than a genuine misalignment between driver anthropometry and seat design. This outcome underscores that the seat dimensions generally align well with the body measurements, supporting ergonomic suitability for drivers in the 95th percentile.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that bus drivers play an essential role in the transportation industry, yet often endure suboptimal working postures that can lead to discomfort and work-related musculoskeletal disorders. The evaluation of working posture among bus drivers in South Cebu, using RULA scores, highlights a pressing issue of ergonomic risks, primarily affecting the neck, trunk, and upper limbs, with specific issues arising from wrist angles, arm flexion, and neck and trunk positions. These findings suggest a need for ergonomic interventions, such as regular breaks, to enhance drivers' safety and comfort.

Furthermore, significant relationships were observed between certain body measurements and ergonomic factors, specifically abdominal depth and elbow angle with cabin dimensions, and buttock-knee length with seat ergonomics. The significant correlation between these measurements and cabin dimensions underscores the importance of these factors in designing driver-friendly workspaces. Despite these key relationships, most body measurements did not show significant effects on cabin or seat ergonomics, suggesting that the current setup accommodates drivers adequately, having little effect on posture and comfort.

The study further assessed the adequacy of cabin and seat dimensions at the 95th percentile of body measurements, finding no statistically significant differences. This indicates that any observed variations were likely due to random differences rather than a true discrepancy, supporting the hypothesis that the current design is broadly suitable for most drivers, accommodating a wide range of anthropometric needs.

Overall, while the existing cabin and seat dimensions are largely adequate for most drivers, targeted ergonomic adjustments and promoting awareness of proper posture, are recommended to address specific posture-related risks identified in the study, which would not only improve drivers' comfort and safety but also potentially increase productivity and job satisfaction.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were drawn to address ergonomic discomforts experienced by bus drivers when driving for a long period. Suggestions that follow would help in creating a more supportive driving environment as well as ensuring a driver's health and efficiency at work are maintained.

1. It is recommended that the company implement regular breaks, allowing drivers time to stretch and alleviate musculoskeletal strain from prolonged, suboptimal postures. During regular breaks, the company can implement a pre-driving stretching routine and stretching breaks for the drivers, where each can take 5 – 10 minutes.

Pre-driving Stretching Routine (5 - 10 minutes)

It is a short stretching set to get the muscles and joints warmed up before driving. This routine consists of neck, shoulders, back, and leg stretches that make them flexible and prevent any kind of strain as they spend periods of long time driving. According to the study of Ghasemi et al. (2018), a stretching routine is essential for reducing the prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) associated with prolonged driving. This will result in higher comfort

levels, reduced strain conditions, and a smaller chance of getting injured during work.

Stretching Breaks (5 - 10 minutes)

It is known that New Librando Transit Inc. buses have rest stops at Guiwanon, Barili, Cebu, as implemented by the company. These stops are planned into the journey to allow passengers and drivers time to rest, use restroom facilities, and sometimes get food. These have an allotted time of 15 - 30 minutes. Given this implementation, bus drivers can utilize their remaining time to perform light stretches. According to the study by Ghasemi and Pirzadeh (2018), incorporating periodic stretching breaks significantly alleviates muscle tension and discomfort associated with long periods of driving, therefore leading to comfort maximization by drivers, further minimizing musculoskeletal disorders risk.

Figures 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, and 26 illustrate the series of steps for the Pre-driving Stretching Routine and Stretching Breaks. These stretches would take 15 – 30 seconds each, and breathing and relaxing between each stretch would help release tightness in the muscles and enhance flexibility, which can reduce the risk of strain or injury and improve the overall effectiveness of the stretch (Sakurai et al., 2024).

2. Drivers should be assigned bus units that correspond to their sizes—small/short, medium/average, or large/tall: Proper sizing of the bus to the driver's dimensions helps improve visibility, ease of control, and ergonomics; such sizing reduces physical stress, the risk of musculoskeletal disorders, improves general driving performance, as well as a safer and more efficient

transportation environment. According to the study by Ha and Park (2024), aligning vehicle size with driver dimensions significantly affects drivers' comfort and control.

These recommendations aim to improve the physical comfort, safety, and overall job satisfaction of bus drivers, which would contribute to their productivity and well-being.

Illustrations	Stretching Exercises	Descriptions
	<p>Neck stretch (Figure 19. Neck stretch)</p>	<p>Tilt your head towards each shoulder, holding for 15 – 30 seconds.</p>
	<p>Shoulder rolls (Figure 20. Shoulder rolls)</p>	<p>Roll your shoulders forward and backward in circular motions.</p>
	<p>Upper back stretch (Figure 21. Upper back stretch)</p>	<p>Interlace fingers and stretch arms forward at your back, straightening your upper back.</p>

Torso twist
(**Figure 22. Torso twist**)

Twist the upper body to each side, using your hand for leverage.

Quadriceps stretch
(**Figure 23. Quadriceps stretch**)

Stand and pull your foot towards your glutes, keeping your knees together. Then switch to the other leg.

Ankle rolls
(**Figure 24. Ankle rolls**)

Lift one foot and roll your ankle in circles, then switch to the other foot.

Hip flexor stretch
(**Figure 25. Hip flexor stretch**)

Step one foot into a lunge position, keeping the back knee on the ground. Then switch to the other foot.

Side stretch
(**Figure 26. Side stretch**)

Stand tall, reach one arm overhead, and lean to the opposite side.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX A

Evaluation of Working Posture: An Action Research Study on the Driving

Posture of New Librando Transit Inc. Bus Drivers

Filling out this survey form indicates that you are giving your informed consent to be a participant in this study and the data collected will be kept confidential.

You are being invited to participate in a research study about the “Evaluation of Working Posture: An Action Research Study on the Driving Posture of New Librando Transit Inc. Bus Drivers”.

Do you agree to accept the invitation?

I agree.

Part I. Profile of the respondents as to;

Please put a check (/) that you belong in the terms of the following:

Last Name, First Name, MI. (Optional): _____

Age:

39-43 years old

44-48 years old

49-53 years old

54-58 years old

59-60 years old

Gender: Male

Female

Years of employment: 5-9 years

10-14 years

15-19 years

20-24 years

25 years and above

Medical History: _____

Height (cm.): _____

Weight (kg.): _____

Part II. Anthropometric body dimensions of bus drivers

Measure the anthropometric characteristics of bus drivers in centimeter or angle degree using measuring tape, anthropometer, and bevel protractor (*Ismaila et al., 2021*).

P. No.	Anthropometric Body Dimensions	Measurements (cm)
P1	Weight	
P2	Sitting Height	
P3	Sitting Eye Height	
P4	Shoulder Width	
P5	Shoulder Height	
P6	Head Length	
P7	Head Breadth	
P8	Shoulder-Elbow Length	
P9	Elbow-Wrist Length	
P10	Hand Length	
P11	Hand Breadth	
P12	Elbow rest height	
P13	Knee Height	
P14	Buttock-Knee Length	
P15	Buttock-Popliteal Length	
P16	Popliteal-Height	
P17	Hip Breadth	
P18	Thigh- Clearance Height	
P19	Abdominal Depth	
P20	Abdominal-Steering	
P21	Chest-Steering	
P22	Foot Length	
P23	Foot Breadth	
P24	Elbow Angle, with Steering	
P25	Elbow Angle with Gear	
P26	Right Knee - Dashboard	
P27	Left Knee - Dashboard	
P28	Knee Angle foot on Floor	
P29	Ankle Angle foot on Pedal	
P30	Back Angle Sitting	

Part III. Dimensions of bus driver cabin

Measure the bus driver cabin parameter in centimeter or angle degree using measuring tape, steel tape, vernier callipers, and bevel protractors (*Ismaila et al., 2021*).

P. No.	Bus Driver Cabin Dimensions	Measurements (cm/°)
P1	Cabin Height	
P2	Cabin Width	
P3	Cabin Length	
P4	Seat to Floor distance	
P5	Pedal to Seat distance	
P6	Steering to Floor	
P7	Dashboard-Backrest distance	
P8	Steering to Backrest distance	
P9	Steering wheel external diameter	
P10	Steering rim thickness	
P11	Pedal Angle	
P12	Dashboard to Seat distance	
P13	Gear lever to Seat distance	

Part IV. Dimensions of bus driver seat

Measure the bus driver seat parameter in centimeter or angle degree using measuring tape, steel tape, vernier callipers, and bevel protractors (*Ismaila et al., 2021*).

P.No.	Bus Driver Seat Dimensions	Measurements (cm/°)
P1	Seat Overall Height	
P2	Seat Height	
P3	Seatpan Thickness	
P4	Seat Width	
P5	Seat Depth	
P6	Backrest Angle	
P7	Backrest Thickness	
P8	Backrest Width (Lumbar level)	
P9	Backrest Width (Shoulder level)	
P10	Backrest Height	
P11	Headrest Angle	
P12	Headrest Width	
P13	Headrest Height (with stand)	
P14	Headrest Height (no stand)	

Part V. RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Observe the driving posture of bus drivers using RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet to determine if they perform either an optimal or improper posture during the 3-hour trip within South Cebu.

RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Complete this worksheet following the step-by-step procedure below. Keep a copy in the employee's personnel folder for future reference.

A. Arm & Wrist Analysis

Step 1: Locate Upper Arm Position

Step 1a: Adjust...

If shoulder is raised: +1;
 If upper arm is abducted: +1;
 If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1

Final Upper Arm Score =

Step 2: Locate Lower Arm Position

Step 2a: Adjust...

If arm is working across midline of the body: +1;
 If arm out to side of body: +1

Final Lower Arm Score =

Step 3: Locate Wrist Position

Step 3a: Adjust...

If wrist is bent from the midline: +1

Final Wrist Score =

Step 4: Wrist Twist

If wrist is twisted mainly in mid-range = 1;
 If twist at or near end of twisting range = 2

Wrist Twist Score =

Step 5: Look-up Posture Score in Table A

Use values from steps 1, 2, 3 & 4 to locate Posture Score in table A.

Posture Score A =

Step 6: Add Muscle Use Score

If posture mainly static (i.e. held for longer than 1 minute) or:
 If action repeatedly occurs 4 times per minute or more: +1

Muscle Use Score =

Step 7: Add Force/load Score

If load less than 2 kg (intermittent): +0;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (intermittent): +1;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (static or repeated): +2;
 If more than 10 kg load or repeated or shocks: +3

Force/load Score =

Step 8: Find Row in Table C

The completed score from the Arm/Wrist analysis is used to find the row on Table C.

Final Wrist & Arm Score =

SCORES

Table A

Upper Arm	Lower Arm	Wrist	1	2	3	4
1	1	1	1	2	3	3
1	2	1	2	3	3	3
1	3	1	3	3	3	3
1	4	1	4	4	4	4
2	1	2	3	3	3	3
2	2	2	3	3	3	3
2	3	2	4	4	4	4
2	4	2	4	4	4	4
3	1	3	4	4	4	4
3	2	3	4	4	4	4
3	3	3	4	4	4	4
3	4	3	4	4	4	4
4	1	4	4	4	4	4
4	2	4	4	4	4	4
4	3	4	4	4	4	4
4	4	4	4	4	4	4
5	1	5	5	5	5	5
5	2	5	5	5	5	5
5	3	5	5	5	5	5
5	4	5	5	5	5	5
6	1	6	6	6	6	6
6	2	6	6	6	6	6
6	3	6	6	6	6	6
6	4	6	6	6	6	6

Table B

Neck	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	1	2	2	1	2	1
1	3	2	3	3	4	5
2	2	3	2	3	4	5
3	3	3	3	4	5	6
4	4	3	4	4	5	6
5	5	4	5	5	6	7
6	6	5	6	6	7	8

Table C

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	1	2	3	4	5	6
2	2	3	4	5	6	7
3	3	3	4	4	5	6
4	3	3	4	4	5	6
5	4	4	5	5	6	7
6	4	4	5	5	6	7
7	5	5	6	6	7	7
8	5	5	6	6	7	7

B. Neck, Trunk & Leg Analysis

Step 9: Locate Neck Position

Step 9a: Adjust...

If neck is twisted: +1; If neck is side-bending: +1

Final Neck Score =

Step 10: Locate Trunk Position

Step 10a: Adjust...

If trunk is twisted: +1; If trunk is side-bending: +1

Final Trunk Score =

Step 11: Legs

If legs & feet supported and balanced: +1;
 If not: +2

Final Leg Score =

Trunk Posture Score

	1	2	3	4	5	6
Legs	1	2	1	2	1	2
Neck	1	2	1	2	1	2
1	1	3	2	3	3	4
2	2	3	2	3	4	5
3	3	3	3	4	5	6
4	4	3	4	4	5	6
5	5	4	5	5	6	7
6	6	5	6	6	7	8

Step 12: Look-up Posture Score in Table B

Use values from steps 8, 9, & 10 to locate Posture Score in Table B.

Posture B Score =

Step 13: Add Muscle Use Score

If posture mainly static or:
 If action 4/minute or more: +1

Muscle Use Score =

Step 14: Add Force/load Score

If load less than 2 kg (intermittent): +0;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (intermittent): +1;
 If 2 kg to 10 kg (static or repeated): +2;
 If more than 10 kg load or repeated or shocks: +3

Force/load Score =

Step 15: Find Column in Table C

The completed score from the Neck/Trunk & Leg analysis is used to find the column on Chart C.

Final Neck, Trunk & Leg Score =

Final Score =

Subject: _____ Date: / / _____
 Company: _____ Department: _____ Scorer: _____

FINAL SCORE: 1 or 2 = Acceptable; 3 or 4 investigate further; 5 or 6 investigate further and change soon; 7 investigate and change immediately

Source: McAtamney, L. & Corlett, E.N. (1993) RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders. *Applied Ergonomics*, 24(2) 91-99.
 © Professor Alan Hedge, Cornell University. Feb. 2001

CURRICULUM VITAE

CURRICULUM VITAE

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